

A typology of European farmers' viewpoints on soil management and an investigation of their context-dependency

Heidi Leonhardt^{a,*}, Michael Braitto^a, Nicole Bütikofer^b, Morten Graversgaard^c, Marion Hacek^a, Jenny Höckert^d, Ernesto Lunar-Koch^a, Christina Lundström^d, Mariella Schreiber^a, Mette Tiselius^d

^a BOKU University, Institute of Sustainable Economic Development, Department of Economics and Social Sciences, Feistmantelstraße 4, 1180 Vienna, Austria

^b Agroscope, Department of Agroecology and Environment, Reckenholzstrasse 191, 8046 Zürich, Switzerland

^c Aarhus University, Department of Agroecology, Blichers Allé 20, 8830 Tjele, Denmark

^d Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences Skara, Department of People and Society, Gråbrödargatan 7, 532 23 Skara, Sweden

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Farmer typology
Farmer viewpoints
Soil management
Q method

ABSTRACT

Fostering the uptake of sustainable soil management practices requires a good understanding of farmers' motivations and priorities. To comprehensively assess these priorities, we identify and describe archetypical viewpoints on soil management among European crop farmers. We analyse interviews conducted with 132 farmers from five case study regions using Q-Methodology, a mixed quantitative and qualitative method. In addition, we apply and compare three different approaches to Q-Methodology and investigate the context-dependency of the identified viewpoints. Our results demonstrate the existence of up to five archetypical viewpoints on soil management. They are distinct in their focus on soil health, farm economics, social sustainability, traditional farming values, and risk avoidance, respectively. We find that these viewpoints are partly—but by no means fully—context-dependent. This implies that farmers' needs do not only vary due to natural farming conditions or farm structural aspects, but also due to subjective worldviews. Knowledge about archetypical viewpoints can help policy makers and advisory services to support farmers in a tailored manner.

1. Introduction

Agricultural soils are vital for producing food, feed, and fibre, while also providing ecosystem services like carbon sequestration and nutrient cycling (Adhikari and Hartemink, 2016; Dominati et al., 2010). However, arable soils are increasingly scarce and degraded, with climate change exacerbating these challenges (Amundson et al., 2015; Verheijen et al., 2009). Practices such as cover cropping, organic fertilization, and conservation tillage offer solutions to improve soil health (Blanchet et al., 2016; Blanchy et al., 2023; de Cárcer et al., 2019). Farmers' adoption of these practices depends on a range of factors, including biophysical, agronomic, financial, institutional, and behavioural aspects (Bartkowski et al., 2022; Dessart et al., 2019; Guillem et al., 2012; Lu et al., 2022; Rust et al., 2020; Thompson et al., 2022). In addition, the priority given to each factor varies between farmers. A holistic approach

is therefore needed to understand the adoption of soil-improving practices on cropland (Heller et al., 2024) and foster their use.

One approach to understanding the complexity of farmers' priorities is through farmer typologies (Lyle, 2015). Such typologies capture diverse opinions while condensing them into a few distinct, typical viewpoints. A well-suited method for developing farmer typologies is Q-Methodology. It combines qualitative (interpretation of interview transcripts) and quantitative (statistical analysis of a sorting exercise) elements to identify different prevailing viewpoints on a topic of interest among the studied population (Zabala et al., 2018). We use this method to address the first aim of our study: developing a typology of European farmers' viewpoints on soil management to better understand farmers' motivations for soil conservation. The corresponding research question is:

* Corresponding author at: BOKU University, Institute of Sustainable Economic Development, Department of Economics and Social Sciences, Feistmantelstraße 4, 1180 Vienna, Austria

E-mail addresses: Heidi.leonhardt@boku.ac.at (H. Leonhardt), michael.braitto@boku.ac.at (M. Braitto), nicole.buetikofer@agroscope.admin.ch (N. Bütikofer), Morten.Graversgaard@agro.au.dk (M. Graversgaard), marion.hacek@boku.ac.at (M. Hacek), Jenny.Hockert@slu.se (J. Höckert), e.lunar-koch@students.boku.ac.at (E. Lunar-Koch), christina.lundstrom@slu.se (C. Lundström), mariella.schreiber@boku.ac.at (M. Schreiber), mette.tiselius@slu.se (M. Tiselius).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2026.109041>

Received 17 April 2025; Received in revised form 10 April 2026; Accepted 11 April 2026

Available online 21 April 2026

0921-8009/© 2026 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

- 1) Which archetypical viewpoints on soil management exist among European cropland farmers?

While farmer typologies have been found to be useful for explaining behaviour (Leonhardt et al., 2022) and informing policy (Huber et al., 2024; Lyle, 2015; Oberlack et al., 2023), they are mostly based on data from single countries or regions (but see Barnes et al., 2022; Casagrande et al., 2016; Soini et al., 2012 for multi-regional typologies). This limits our understanding of how much contextual factors (e.g., societal or biophysical) matter for farmers' viewpoints and whether existing typologies can be transferred to other contexts. The second aim of our work is therefore to explore the context-dependency of the identified viewpoints on soil management. To this end, we collect and analyse data from multiple case study regions in Europe that differ in their biophysical and institutional setting using Q-Methodology. While sometimes applied in other fields (Seghezzo et al., 2023), analysis methods for multi-regional Q-Methodology data have never been applied to farmer typologies. We use and compare three such methods and additionally discuss the influence of farm structural and biophysical aspects on farmer viewpoints to address the research question:

- 2) To what extent are these archetypical viewpoints influenced by contextual factors?

Using Q-Methodology to develop a (farmer) typology “offers a middle ground between the structure of surveys and the depth of interviews, and combines advantages of both” (Zabala et al., 2018, p. 1187). It provides a structured and replicable way of eliciting farmers' social perspectives while providing a holistic and qualitative picture, as participants are required to consider all relevant aspects of their opinion simultaneously (Sneegas et al., 2021; Watts and Stenner, 2012). Q-Methodology can also identify marginalized or otherwise hidden views as it facilitates their deliberation (Zabala et al., 2018), rendering it useful for facilitating stakeholder engagement (Usher et al., 2023). Its results have successfully been used to support (environmental, conservation, and agricultural) policy making at several stages of the policy process, including the assessment of policy options and their acceptability, policy appraisal, decision making, and consensus building (Huber et al., 2024; Mukherjee et al., 2018; Seghezzo et al., 2023; Sneegas et al., 2021; Zabala et al., 2018). As a result, Q-Methodology is popular in conservation-related studies, including agriculture (Dieteren et al., 2023; Seghezzo et al., 2023).

While Q-Methodology has been successfully used to develop farmer typologies (Davies and Hodge, 2012; Davies and Hodge, 2007; Vecchio et al., 2022; Walder and Kantelhardt, 2018) or typologies of farming stakeholders' viewpoints (Iversen et al., 2024; Ober et al., 2025) it has, to the best of our knowledge, never been applied in a multi-regional context for this purpose. Moreover, we are not aware of any farmer typologies (using Q-Methodology or other methods) that focus on soil management, with the exception of Braitto et al. (2020).

Existing typologies of farmers' viewpoints, identities, or (management) styles mostly focus on practice adoption, policy responses, or ecological awareness (Bartkowski et al., 2022). Recurring farmer types include *Productivists*, who prioritize economic outcomes and yields, *Innovators*, who embrace change and new practices, *Environmentalists* or *Conservationists*, who prioritize environmental sustainability, and *Diversifiers*, *Traditionalists*, and *Pragmatists* (Bartkowski et al., 2022; Emtage et al., 2007). Similar types related to soil management also appear in Braitto et al.'s (2020) typology.

Our study contributes to the literature in several ways. First, we are the first to explore European farmers' viewpoints on soil management—a priority in EU policy (EC, 2026; Heuser, 2022)—based on data from multiple regions. Our study will therefore offer novel insights for the design of targeted soil conservation support measures. Second, by examining the context-dependency of these viewpoints by means of the (to the best of our knowledge) first multi-country Q-Methodology study

on farmers, we provide insights into the transferability of typology study results to other contexts. Third, we advance Q-Methodology by comparing different approaches for multi-regional analyses, contributing to its methodological development.

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows. We first briefly introduce the five case study regions located in Austria, Denmark, Spain, Sweden, and Switzerland. We then describe Q-Methodology and our methodological approach in section 3. Section 4 presents our results regarding research question 1, which we discuss and interpret with regards to research question 2 in section 5.

2. Case study regions

The case study regions were the *Weinviertel* in north-east Austria, *West and South Zealand* in eastern Denmark, *Guadalajara* in central Spain, the *Plain Areas of Svealand* in Eastern Sweden, and the *Central Plateau* that stretches across Switzerland (see Fig. 1). These regions cover five major environmental zones of Europe (Metzger et al., 2012) where topography, soil, and climatic conditions differ. Most regions experience an increase in spring and (early) summer droughts due to climate change, necessitating cropland management changes. Irrigation is partly prevalent in Guadalajara, but not significant elsewhere. Farm structure and farming practices also vary between regions, as shown in Table 1.¹

3. Data and methods

Q-Methodology allows researchers to study human subjectivity by identifying a finite number of distinct viewpoints on a given topic (Dieteren et al., 2023; Watts and Stenner, 2012). It is similar to traditional factor analysis, but ‘flipped around’: factors in Q-Methodology cluster (views shared by) *groups of participants*. The method hence treats study participants' views, expressed in a so-called ‘Q-sort’, as variables to correlate and group (Watts and Stenner, 2012).

In practice, Q-Methodology researchers ask a selected set of participants (the ‘P-set’) to sort a set of statements on the issue of interest (the ‘Q-set’) according to their level of (dis-)agreement or importance. The resulting ‘Q-sorts’ are then factor-analysed to develop and describe viewpoints (Watts and Stenner, 2012). A Q-Methodological study comprises five main steps: development of the Q-set, selection of the P-set, the Q-sorting procedure (data collection), Q-factor analysis, and viewpoint description (factor interpretation) (McKeown and Thomas, 2013). Fig. 2 summarizes these steps graphically, as implemented in our study.

3.1. Q-set

The Q-set, typically a set of verbal statements about the topic under study, allows study participants to express their views in a structured manner. It must comprise all aspects that could be used to express one's views, but still be of a manageable size (McKeown and Thomas, 2013; Watts and Stenner, 2012). We developed our Q-set based on literature on farmer (soil management) behaviour, nine stakeholder interviews, and the project teams' knowledge. We initially compiled 360 items grouped into seven categories: attitudes/values, economics, environment/soil, farm(er) context, institutional context, knowledge/experience, and society. We then merged related items, harmonized their wording to “When I work with my soil, it is important for me...”, and translated them to local languages. We conducted ten pre-tests to add/remove items and test the wording. The resulting Q-set of 45 statements

¹ Figure 1 and Table 1 show information at the level of the NUTS-2 regions (NUTS: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics; NUTS-2: 2nd largest NUTS units) where the case studies were located. In some countries, the case study region spanned more than one NUTS-2 region. For simplicity, we present only data from the NUTS-2 region where most interviews were done.

Fig. 1. Location of the case study regions at NUTS-2 level. Created using package eurostat (Lahti et al., 2023; Lahti et al., 2017) in R (R Core Team, 2021). Data source: Eurostat.

Table 1
Information on the structure of agriculture in the NUTS-2 regions where case study regions are (primarily) located.

NUTS-2 regions; variables	Unit of measurement	DK02	ES42	AT12	SE12	CH02
Livestock per ha	LSU/ha UAA	0.78	0.38	0.59	0.42	1.46
Avg. farm size	ha UAA	80	38	31	69	23
Organic area	% of total UAA	7.08	3.11	23.53	21.98	13.66
Share conservation tillage	%	14.90	18.89	38.39	13.45 ¹	26.29 ²
Share no-till	%	1.22	3.29	2.19	1.07 ¹	3.64 ²
AECM: supported area	% of total UAA	12.83	3.70	95.09	99.73	no data
AECM: payments	Euro/supported ha	2064.60	601.03	2064.82	1322.30	no data
Non-family labour	% of total AWU	34.01	26.36	16.82	26.79	27.52
Female farm managers ³	% of farm managers	11.8	28.1	36.7	17.2	5.3
Avg. age farm managers ³	age	62.3	64.1	52.7	61.3	54.6

Notes: Unless marked otherwise, data are from Eurostat (<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/main/data/database>) and for the latest available years at the time of writing (mostly 2016 or 2020). ¹ Data for entire country; shares are higher regionally but no data were available. ² Data for entire country, source: <https://www.agrarbericht.ch>. ³ A farm manager is “the person responsible for the normal financial and production routines of running the holding” (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:Manager_of_agricultural_holding). LSU: Livestock Units. UAA: Utilized Agricultural Area. AECM: Agri-Environment-Climate Measures. AWU: Annual Work Units. NUTS: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics.

was printed on small cards. Appendix A lists all statements, main sources, and statement categories.

3.2. P-Set

Participants for a Q-Methodological study are typically purposefully selected to cover a wide range of potential views (Watts and Stenner, 2012). Our population of interest were the main decision makers of farms in the case study regions who farmed cropland, typically farm owner-managers or managers. Among this population, we interviewed farmers with different backgrounds and farm contexts: large—small farms, organic—conventional farms, conventional tillage—reduced tillage, mixed farms—pure crop farms, male—female, older—younger, and more, depending on the structure of farming in each case study. We recruited participants via farm databases (Denmark), farmer associations, advisory services, and farmer federations (Austria, Spain, Sweden), newsletters and social media posts (Switzerland), complemented by online searches, personal networks, and snowballing. We asked to interview the farms’ main decision makers, which were mostly individuals, sometimes two people.

We interviewed the main decision makers of 132 farms: 30 in the Austrian case study, 20 in Denmark, 23 in Spain, 33 in Sweden, and 26 in

Switzerland. Four Q-sorts were excluded from the analysis² and on one farm, the two main decision-makers completed one Q-sort each, such that 129 Q-sorts from 128 farms entered the analysis. Table 2 gives an overview of participants’ farm structural and demographic information by case study.

3.3. Interviews

The Q-sorting procedure typically takes place as part of an interview (Dieteren et al., 2023). We conducted semi-structured in-person interviews with three parts: 1) A warm-up phase, where participants described their farm and soil management strategies; 2) the Q-sorting, including explanations, the sorting procedure, and post-sorting questions; and 3) questions on farming ideals and norms (analysed in Schreiber et al., 2026). In the end, participants filled out a short questionnaire on demographics, farm structural information, soil

² One participant considered the Q-sorting too difficult to complete. Another participant did not properly understand the task which resulted in an inconsistent sort. On two farms, pairs of decision-makers (husband and wife) completed a single but inconsistent Q-sort together.

Fig. 2. Q-Methodological approach taken in this study.

Table 2
Information about participants and their farms by case study region.

		Full sample	AT	DK	ES	SE	CH
Total participants	N	129	31	20	23	32	23
Gender	female	9	2	1	2	3	1
	male	120	29	19	21	29	22
Age	mean	49.9	45.8	55.1	51.5	50.5	48.6
	(min-max)	(21–72)					
	no	11	2	0	0	7	2
Agricultural education	lower	40	5	11	8	10	6
	higher	49	16	6	9	7	11
	university	28	8	2	6	8	4
Farm type ¹	N.A.	1	0	1	0	0	0
	field only	72	21	9	20	14	7
	has livestock	49	6	5	2	16	20
Farmed cropland (ha)	mean	254.2	291.3	284.1	314.4	325.0	20.7
	(min-max)	(2–>1500)					
Rented land (ha)	mean	139.4	71.9	155.7	205.1	225.7	13.6
	(min-max)	(0–>1000)					
Organic farming	yes	38	11	3	0	13	11
	no	83	20	15	22	17	9
	partly	8	0	2	1	2	3
Farm operated ²	full-time	86	16	19	22	23	6
	part-time	23	3	1	1	9	9
	N.A.	20	12	0	0	0	8
Crop rotation	avg. no. of crops	6.0	7.1	6.4	5.5	5.1	5.8

Notes: ¹ Farms neither classified as “field only” or “has livestock” are mixed farms with permanent crops, seed production, or horticulture. ² In Austria and Switzerland, the question on part-time or full-time farming was only added to the questionnaire after the first interviews had already been completed so that this information is missing (N.A.) for some farms. AT: Austria. DK: Denmark. ES: Spain. SE: Sweden. CH: Switzerland. Very large farm sizes anonymized.

management, and farming ideals; anonymized data are provided in Leonhardt et al. (2025b). Supplementary material A provides the interview guideline and questionnaire (see also H. Leonhardt et al., 2025c). The interviews were conducted in local languages (Danish, German, Spanish, Swedish) and mostly on participants' farms. They typically lasted between 30 min and two hours.

In the Q-sorting procedure, participants respond to the items of the Q-set by ranking them according to their agreement (Watts and Stenner, 2012). The second panel in Fig. 2 depicts the forced-distribution sorting grid we used. Participants first read all statements and sorted them into three piles: agree, disagree, and neutral. We then instructed them to fill the grid, beginning at one end. Agreement with the statements tended to be high, i.e., statements sorted around the centre were usually still from

the “agree” pile. Once they completed their sorting, participants were given the opportunity to revise their Q-sort if desired. We then photographed it for later digitization and asked participants to explain their sorting in brief post-sorting interviews (McKeown and Thomas, 2013; Watts and Stenner, 2012). The raw Q-sort data are provided in Leonhardt et al. (2025a).

3.4. Q-factor analysis and factor interpretation

The Q-factor analysis follows a typical (but inverted) factor analysis procedure to identify and extract patterns of similarity from participants' digitized Q-sorts (Dieteren et al., 2023). We used the software KADE (Banasick, 2019) for analysis, and followed the process outlined in Watts

and Stenner (2012). We conducted three different Q-factor analyses: (a) a composite analysis, where we factor-analysed all 129 Q-sorts together, which results in an overall typology of all interviewed farmers, (b) a first-order analysis, i.e., five separate analyses per case study region, which results in five typologies (one per case study region), and (c) a second-order analysis of the factors that resulted from the first-order analysis, which results in a ‘meta-typology’ of the five case-specific typologies (Seghezze et al., 2023).

We used principal-component analysis and varimax rotation for all analyses. Statistical significance levels were set to $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$. To decide on the number of factors to extract we used Eigenvalues (>1), % variance explained (the more the better), the number of loading participants (at least 2), and the meaningfulness and salience of factors by testing several different solutions. In two cases of the first-order (i.e., case-specific) analysis, two- or three-factor solutions appeared equally feasible and interpretable. In both cases we opted for the three-factor solution to increase viewpoint variety. We ‘flagged’ participants to define a factor if they loaded on only this one factor in a statistically significant way.

We interpreted factors and developed narrative viewpoint descriptions based on factor arrays, z-scores, and the post-sorting interviews. Factor arrays show the average ranking of each statement in the sorting grid. z-scores describe the average level of (dis-)agreement a factor expresses with each statement. Particularly relevant for interpretation were those statements that were ranked very high/low (at +4 or -4) by a factor, and statements that were ranked (statistically significantly) higher/lower by a factor compared to all other factors, summarized in so-called “crib sheets” (Watts and Stenner, 2012). To evaluate the factor-specific relevance of the Q-set’s themes (i.e., statement categories) we conducted a salience analysis (Webler et al., 2009) for the composite and second-order factors. To do so, we calculated the normalized sum of the z-scores of all statements belonging to one category by factor and compared them across factors (Webler et al., 2009).

The first-order analysis results of the Austrian and Swedish case study region were presented to the respective participants in in-person workshops, where they were asked to reflect on the typology. This did not result in any changes to these two typologies.³ We did not conduct any further post-Q interviews with (highly-loading) participants to validate narratives (Webler et al., 2009). An artist was hired to create graphical illustrations of the farmer types of the composite analysis based on the narrative viewpoint descriptions.

4. Results

4.1. Composite analysis

The composite analysis resulted in a five-factor solution. Together, the five factors account for 56% of the study variance. 94 participants are significantly associated with a single factor; 35 are not (4 Austrian, 1 Swiss, 6 Danish, 8 Spanish, and 16 Swedish participants; most of these are associated with 2 factors). Appendix C shows the defining participants per factor. Table 3 presents statement z-scores and hypothetical statement rankings (factor arrays) by factor. Demographic/farm structural information for the farms loading on each factor and statistical information are presented in Table 4. Appendix B provides the results of the salience analysis.

We labelled the viewpoints that resulted from factor interpretation as *Soil farmers*, *Economic farmers*, *Sustainability farmers*, *Practical farmers*, and *Risk-averse farmers*. We summarize their main characteristics in the narrative viewpoint descriptions below. Numbers in parentheses refer to statement numbers and hypothetical statement rankings (cf. Table 3);

³ In the other case study regions, we did not conduct such workshops due to time constraints by the research team or a lack of interest by participants.

codes such as ‘CH02’ refer to participant IDs. We also provide participants’ association with a factor when quoting them (cf. Appendix B). An asterisk (*) indicates that a statement was ranked statistically significantly different compared to other factors. ‘Consensus statements’ are those that do not differ between any pair of factors at $p < 0.05$.

4.1.1. Viewpoint FC1: soil farmers

For farmers sharing viewpoint FC1, the greatest priorities in soil management are to preserve the soil for future generations (2: +4) and to increase soil organic carbon (40: +4), a farm’s “elixir of life” (CH02, FC1: 0.82). Soil health and the environment are generally a priority for FC1: impacts on soil organisms (34*: +3) and the environment at large (32*: +2) are very important, as is working together with nature (33*: +3) and considering climatic changes (44*: +1). Preventing nutrient losses (41: +2) is comparatively relevant, too. The salience analysis confirms this, showing that FC1 ranks ‘environment and soil’ statements highest, and higher than all other factors. Conversely, FC1 generally ranks ‘economics’ statements lower than all others. Buyers’ requirements (29: -1) or a fields’ ownership status (11: -4) are of little or no relevance for FC1. Farmer SE05 illustrates this: “My fields have all improved since I started. It is my goal to leave behind a better land even though I only lease.” The very low importance ascribed to short-term crop yields (7*: -3) or profits (5: -4, consensus with FC3) underlines the long-term orientation of FC1’s soil management.

In summary, *soil farmers* exhibit a long-term orientation in soil management, aim to keep and increase soil health for future generations to come, and strive to avoid detrimental impacts on the environment. Fig. 3 provides a graphical illustration of *soil farmers’* priorities, created by an artist.

4.1.2. Viewpoint FC2: economic farmers

For viewpoint FC2, it is of utmost relevance to increase the soil’s water retention capacity (45*: +4) and to ensure their farm’s long-term economic viability (4: +4, consensus with FC3). In general, FC2 prioritizes economic aspects in soil management, ranking the related statements higher on average than any other factor. Farmers sharing this viewpoint consider harvesting good yields an important goal in the short (7*: +1) and long run (38: +3, consensus with FC3). Similarly, careful cost calculation (3: +3), efficient use of machinery (42: +2) and working time (18: +2), and making good short-term profits (5*: +2) are more relevant than for others. Functional aspects of soil health, such as preventing pests (27: +2) and increasing soil organic carbon (40: +3), take precedence over others. ES01 (FC2: 0.69) illustrates this: “a soil with organic matter withstands drought much better, for example. And so, increasing organic matter and reducing erosion is the most important thing”. It is less important for FC2 than for others to account for farm successors (9: 0) or to rely on research-based recommendations (23: -1) or colleagues’ experiences (13: -2). FC2 does not consider it important to avoid conflict with legal regulations (24*: -3), and is not influenced by subsidies (6: -3). Impacts on neighbours (17: -4) and others’ opinion (35: -4, consensus with FC4) were ranked lowest, in line with the salience analysis, which shows that FC2 ranks ‘society’ related statements lower than all others, and illustrated by ES04 (FC2: 0.55): “I don’t care if they say I do right or I do wrong”.

In summary, *economic farmers* strive to organize soil management in an economically efficient way and emphasize the functional aspects—especially soil water retention capacity—of soil health to ensure their farm’s long-term economic viability. Fig. 4 illustrates these main priorities.

4.1.3. Viewpoint FC3: sustainability farmers

Viewpoint FC3’s top priorities in soil management are to enjoy their work (36*: +4) and to ensure their farm’s long-term economic viability (4*: +4, same as FC2), which is, according to SE31 (FC3: 0.65) “the basis of it all”. In addition, it is comparatively important for FC3 to avoid impacts on neighbours (17*: +2) and the environment (32: +2,

Table 3
Factor arrays and z-scores of factors FC1-FC5, extracted in the composite analysis.

Factor	Statement	FC1		FC2		FC3		FC4		FC5	
		Rank	z-sc.								
1	... that my plots look tidy and neat.	-2	-1.17	0	0.11	-2	-0.9	3*	1.3	0	-0.02
2	... to preserve the soil for future generations.	4	1.83	1	0.36	3	1.04	1	0.72	3	1.47
3	... to consider the costs involved.	0	-0.26	3	1.14	2	0.87	0	-0.07	4	1.71
4	... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	3	1.26	4	1.7	4*	2.36	2	0.79	3	1.49
5	... to prioritize short-term profit	-4	-1.88	2*	0.94	-4	-1.81	-2	-1.02	-1	-0.35
6	... to receive subsidies for what I do.	-2	-1.19	-3	-1.25	-4*	-1.77	2	1	3	1.38
7	... to maximize crop yields in this year.	-3*	-1.34	1*	0.94	0	0.21	-1	-0.57	1	0.07
8	... how far a plot is away from the farmhouse.	-3	-1.34	-2	-0.91	0	0.27	-1	-0.28	-3	-1.66
9	... to hand it over to my successors in a good condition.	3	1.39	0	0.14	3	1.06	3	1.4	1	0.55
10	... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to. ... to make a difference between the land I own and the land I do not own myself.	-1	-0.42	-1	-0.42	-2*	-1.02	1	0.44	2	1.07
11	... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	-4	-1.74	-1*	-0.78	-3	-1.46	-3	-1.64	-4	-1.88
12	... to rely on the experiences of colleagues.	-1	-0.45	-1	-0.79	-3*	-1.31	-1	-0.46	0	-0.04
13	... to rely on my own practical experiences.	0	-0.22	-2	-0.91	-1	-0.49	-1	-0.36	0	0
14	... to do what I believe in.	1	0.66	1	0.64	1	0.59	4*	1.81	0	-0.07
15	... to consider how neighbouring plots are farmed.	1	0.47	3	1.18	3	1	4	1.46	1	0.29
16	... to consider how my actions impact my neighbourhood.	-3	-1.51	-3	-1.31	-3	-1.61	-4	-1.89	-4	-2.13
17	... to minimize working time.	-1	-0.76	-4	-1.4	2*	0.82	-3	-1.81	-1	-0.28
18	... to rely on traditional, handed-down knowledge.	-1	-0.71	2	0.97	-1	-0.84	-2	-0.94	1	0.76
19	... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	-1	-0.56	-3	-1.38	-3	-1.25	0	0.38	-1	-0.28
20	... how long I will continue to farm.	0	-0.21	0	-0.4	-1	-0.32	0	0.01	-1	-0.29
21	... that I don't have to deal with more bureaucracy than necessary.	-2	-1.26	-2	-1.01	-2	-1.01	-3	-1.25	-2	-1.12
22	... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	-2	-0.85	1	0.39	1	0.58	0	0.24	-3	-1.31
23	... not to come in conflict with legal regulations.	0	-0.27	-1	-0.47	1	0.44	1	0.57	0	0.02
24	... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather events.	0*	-0.2	-3*	-1.39	1	0.45	2	0.75	2	1.05
25	... to reduce soil erosion.	1	0.67	-1	-0.5	0	-0.15	-2	-0.78	3	1.31
26	... to prevent pests.	2	1.08	1	0.78	-2*	-0.88	1	0.41	2	0.86
27	... to know the plot's soil quality data.	0	0.25	2	0.96	-1	-0.5	0	-0.03	1	0.57
28	... to meet the requirements of my buyers.	0	0.25	0	-0.17	0	0.24	1	0.47	-2*	-0.98
29	... to meet the expectations of society.	-1	-0.41	0	-0.3	2	0.92	0	0.34	2	0.85
30	... to produce food for society.	-2	-0.92	-2	-1.18	0*	-0.22	-3	-1.78	-3	-1.21
31	... how my actions impact the environment.	1	0.55	-1	-0.49	-1	-0.67	2	0.79	1	0.48
32	... that I work together with nature.	2*	1.09	0	0.17	2	0.68	0	-0.02	0	-0.13
33	... how my actions impact soil organisms such as earthworms.	3*	1.16	0	-0.25	0	0.34	0	0.15	-1	-0.29
34	... how others perceive my actions.	-3	-1.3	-4	-2.29	-1*	-0.39	-4	-2.42	-3	-1.21
35	... that the work gives me pleasure.	2	1.11	2	1.09	4*	2.13	3	1.27	-1*	-0.37
36	... to avoid economic risks.	-1	-0.35	0	0.35	1	0.48	-1	-0.34	4*	2.28
37	... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	1	0.9	3	1.63	3	1.85	2	1.17	2	0.77
38	... that I try new practices.	0	0.42	-1	-0.87	1	0.53	-2	-0.58	-2	-0.89
39	... to increase organic matter.	4	1.41	3	1.2	0	0.04	1	0.59	0	0.06
40	... to prevent nutrient losses.	2	1.04	1	0.77	1	0.63	1	0.54	0	-0.24
41	... to minimize machinery use.	0	-0.29	2	1.08	-1	-0.65	0	0.01	1	0.35
42	...to protect water resources.	2	1.06	0	0.35	2	0.69	3	1.23	-1*	-0.44
43	...to consider climatic changes.	1*	0.74	-2	-0.94	0*	0.04	-2	-1.12	-2	-1.12
44	...to increase the soil's water retention capacity.	1*	1.03	4*	1.76	-2*	-1.12	-1	-0.39	0	0.07

Note: * indicates statements that are ranked statistically significantly different by this factor compared to all others. Italics indicates consensus statements. Ranks refer to statements' placement in the Q sorting grid/factor arrays (see Fig. 2).

Table 4

Demographic and farm structural information of participants loading on factors FC1-FC5 and statistical information about factors.

Demographic and farm structural information by factor		Full sample	FC1	FC2	FC3	FC4	FC5	Not flagged
N participants	Total	129	58	15	14	4	3	35
	AT	31	24	2			1	4
	DK	20	6		8			6
	ES	23	4	9		1	1	8
	SE	32	5	4	6	1		16
	CH	23	19			2	1	1
Gender	female	9	6	1		1		1
	male	120	52	14	14	3	3	34
Age	mean	49.9	48.8	49.8	54.6	55.0	45.7	49.5
	(min-max)	(21–72)						
Agricultural education	no	11	5	2	1	1		2
	lower	40	15	4	8		1	12
	higher	49	26	4	2	1	1	15
	university	28	11	5	3	2	1	6
Farm type	N.A.	1	1					
	field only	72	32	13	6	2	1	17
	has livestock	49	26	1	6	2	1	13
Farmed cropland (ha)	mean	254.18	197.77	359.60	312.71	201.75	52.33	300.74
	(min-max)	(2 - >1500)						
Rented land (ha)	mean	139.38	79.72	237.40	214.43	40.00	37.00	177.19
	(min-max)	(0 - >1000)						
Organic	yes	38	22	1	3	2	1	9
	no	83	33	14	9	2	2	23
	partly	8	3		2			3
Farm operated	full-time	86	30	14	13	2	1	26
	part-time	23	11	1	1	1	1	8
	N.A.	20	17			1	1	1
Crop rotation	avg. number of crops	6.0	6.4	5.9	5.2	5.0	4.3	5.7
Statistical information by factor								
Eigenvalues (after rotation)			34.14	11.02	13.72	7.35	5.65	
% explained variance			26	9	11	6	4	
No. of defining Q-sorts			58	15	14	4	3	
Std. error of factor z-scores			0.063	0.126	0.134	0.243	0.277	
Correlation between factors								
Factor FC1			1.00	0.48	0.57	0.55	0.33	
Factor FC2				1.00	0.37	0.48	0.38	
Factor FC3					1.00	0.43	0.24	
Factor FC4						1.00	0.45	
Factor FC5							1.00	

Fig. 3. Illustration of viewpoint FC1, soil farmers. © freihand-zeichner.at.

Fig. 4. Illustration of viewpoint FC2, economic farmers. © freihand-zeichner.at.

consensus with FC1), and to respond to society's expectations (30*: 0). The latter is confirmed by the salience analysis ('society' statements being ranked higher than by any other factor, although still around 0) and in stark contrast to all other viewpoints, potentially because some

Fig. 5. Illustration of viewpoint FC3, sustainability farmers. © freihand-zeichner.at.

Fig. 6. Illustration of viewpoint FC4, practical farmers. © freihand-zeichner.at.

FC3-defining farmers are active in their local community and feel responsible for its wellbeing. Others are more ambivalent about society's demands and perceive a divide between farmers and society. Further aspects that differentiate FC3 from others include the importance given to driving distances (8: 0) and their openness to new practices (39: +1), as opposed to relying on their (sometimes considered outdated) education (12*: -3). Several soil health related aspects are unimportant (26*: -2; 45*: -2; see also salience analysis results), potentially because these issues are not relevant on the defining participants' farms. Farmers sharing FC3 further do not consider minimizing machinery use (42: -1) or restricting themselves to the machines available on their own farm (10*: -2) as important: "If I know something that I want to try or test something new, then I usually just hire that service" (SE26; FC3: 0.62). Finally, FC3 does not at all consider subsidies (6*: -4) or short-term profits (5: -4, consensus with FC1) as important drivers of soil management.

Fig. 7. Illustration of viewpoint FC5, risk-averse farmers. © freihand-zeichner.at.

In summary, *sustainability farmers*, illustrated in Fig. 5, strive to ensure the long-term economic sustainability of their farm while considering societal needs and environmental impacts. They are open to novel practices and, above all, want to enjoy their work.

4.1.4. Viewpoint FC4: practical farmers

For viewpoint FC4, relying on one's own practical experiences (14*: +4) and doing what one believes in (15: +4) are top priorities in soil management. FC4 gives importance to fields' appearance (1*: +3), as "there is nothing as beautiful as a freshly ploughed field" (SE09; FC4: 0.56), and strives to provide food for society (31: +2). This suggests a worldview that upholds traditional and productivist farming values, as supported by the salience analysis results which show that 'attitude/value' statements are ranked higher by FC4 than by all others. Farmer CH12 (FC4: 0.58) illustrates this view: "I see myself as a food producer. That's what I want to do with my job. Even if I'm organic, I want to produce. I don't want to be, let's say, a landscape gardener." The farmers associated with FC4 want to enjoy their work with the soil (36: +3) as "the work has to be enjoyable, otherwise you don't want to do it" (CH12). Like for FC1 and FC3, it is important for FC4 to preserve the soil for successors (9: +3) and to protect water resources (43: +3). To achieve these goals, FC4 relies, more than others, on soil quality data (28: +1), and traditional knowledge (19: 0). In general, statements related to (using existing) 'knowledge and experience' and to the 'institutional context' are ranked higher by FC4 than by others. Minimizing work time (18: -2) is irrelevant, underlining the appreciation for hands-on farm work. FC4 does not aim to mitigate impacts of extreme weather events through soil management (25: -2), perhaps because they do not perceive them as such: Farmer SE09 states that "for me this is not a climate crisis, what we are in right now. Because this has happened before." Of lowest importance for FC4 are considering neighbouring plots (16: -4, consensus with FC5) and others' perceptions of their work (35: -4, consensus with FC2), underlined by CH12: "I don't really care what others think of me. It must be right for me".

In summary, *practical farmers* prioritize many aspects associated with a traditional farming life. They like accurate and practical farm work that makes for a tidy farm and feeds society, see value in traditional, handed-down knowledge and their own beliefs, and aim to hand a

Table 5 Summary of first-order analysis results by case study region.

Case study country	Consensus aspects (+)	Viewpoint ID and name	Main characteristics (+)	N loading participants
Austria ¹	Erosion prevention, future generations, pest prevention	AT F1 Food production as a lifestyle	Food production, joy at work, future generations, practical work	14
		AT F2 Optimizing the farm business for the long-term	Compliance with regulations, efficiency & optimization	4
		AT F3 Soil health for economic sustainability	Soil health, long-term economic viability	11
Denmark	Long-term focus, joy at work, own beliefs, environment	DK F1 Doing what's right for the soil	Soil health, environment	12
		DK F2 Innovation for successors and the community	Society and neighbourhood, long-term focus, innovation	3
		DK F3: Pragmatic stewards: balancing tradition, economics, joy and soil health	Pragmatism, stability, others' opinion	4
		ES F1 Doing what's right for the soil	Soil health and functions, future generations, own beliefs	10
Spain	Yield stability, pest prevention	ES F2 Efficiently managing risks	Short-term & long-term business results, efficiency, risk avoidance	7
		ES F3 Open-mindedness for economics and ecology	Soil and environment, openness to others	5
		SE F1 Ecological sustainability for the future: environment, soil health and climate	Future generations, joy at work, environment and nature, soil health	10
Sweden	Soil fertility, own beliefs, yield stability	SE F2 Economizing the farm business: economics and practical experience	Own beliefs, economic aspects, yields, practical experience	9
		SE F3 Farming pragmatically for the future: careful, pragmatic and a bit conservative	Future generations, soil health, enjoy farming lifestyle	5
		CH F1 Soil health for the future	Future generations, soil health, environment	17
Switzerland ²	Long-term focus	CH F2 Food production by conviction	Joy at work, food production, compliance with law and own beliefs	4

(continued on next page)

Table 5 (continued)

Case study country	Consensus aspects (+)	Viewpoint ID and name	Main characteristics (+)	N loading participants
		CH_F3 <i>Efficient work for economic security</i>	Risk avoidance, buyers' requirements, farm economics	2

Note: Consensus aspects and main characteristics refer primarily to items ranked on the positive side of the Q-sort, which were typically more distinguishing and salient than those on the negative side. ¹ See also Leonhardt et al. (2025). ² See also Bütikofer et al. (2024).

healthy soil over to farm successors. Fig. 6 provides a graphical illustration of this viewpoint.

4.1.5. Viewpoint FC5: risk-averse farmers

Viewpoint FC5's soil management is primarily determined by avoiding financial risk (37*: +4) and carefully considering costs (3: +4), as "at the end of the day, you have to be able to pay the bills and that's why it's important ... to minimize or reduce the risks" (CH06; FC5: 0.52). This ensures the farm's long-term economic viability (4: +3, consensus with FC1). Other statement rankings as well as the salience analysis results also underline FC5's desire for financial stability and frugality and the priority given to the statements classified as (farm) 'economics'. Receiving subsidies is considered important (6: +3) despite the associated paperwork (22: -3), as is working with machines already available (10: +2) and mitigating risks from extreme weather events (25: +3). Many soil-related aspects are less important for FC5 (41: 0; 28*: -2; 34*: -2). Similarly, it is relatively unimportant to work together with nature (33: -1) or to protect water resources (43*: -1). Enjoying one's work

(36*: -1) is of (comparatively) low relevance to FC5's soil management decisions, too. Neighbouring plots (16: -4, consensus with FC4) and plot ownership (11: -4, consensus with FC1) are ranked lowest, as CH06 puts it: "I want to manage [the land] in the long term, regardless of whether it belongs to me or not, and then it is in my interest to take care of it". The salience analysis also confirms this low relevance of the 'farm(er) context' for FC5's soil management.

In summary, risk-averse farmers focus on avoiding financial risks, including those originating from extreme weather events, and unnecessary costs. Environmental and soil health-related considerations or enjoying work are subordinate to this paramount goal. This viewpoint's priorities are illustrated in Fig. 7.

4.1.6. Consensus statements

There is statistically significant consensus among all five factors on two statements: Advisory services are seen as neither important nor unimportant for soil management by all viewpoints (20: 0, 0, -1, 0, -1); and how long one expects to continue farming (e.g., due to retirement approaching) is seen as relatively unimportant by all (21: -2, -2, -2, -3, -2). Other aspects that stand out as being either very important or unimportant, although without statistically significant consensus across all factors, include the following: It is unimportant for all to consider how neighbouring plots are farmed (16: -3, -3, -3, -4, -4); and for all but FC2 whether a specific plot is owned or not (11: -4, -1, -3, -3, -4). Relying on the latest recommendations from research is ranked around the centre of the distribution by all factors (23: 0, -1, 1, 1, 0). Ensuring a stable yield is generally considered important (38: +1, +3, +3, +2, +2), as is ensuring the farm's long-term economic viability (4: +3, +4, +4, +2, +3).

Fig. 8. Participants' association with the viewpoints resulting from each method. Each line represents one Q-sort and its association with viewpoints from the composite analysis (FC1-FC5), the first-order analysis (viewpoints AT_F1-SE_F3) and the second-order analysis (FO1-FO3b). Colour coding refers to the composite analysis. Those Q-sorts not associated with a (single) viewpoint are captured in the boxes marked with asterisks. Created with packages ggplot2 (Wickham, 2016) and ggaluvial (Brunson and Read, 2020) in R (R Core Team, 2021).

4.2. First-order analysis

The first-order analysis resulted in three factors per case study. Supplementary material B provides full results for all 15 factors, including narrative viewpoint descriptions. Table 5 gives an overview of their most distinctive aspects. 12 participants did not load significantly on any (one) of the respective case study viewpoints, 8 of them from Sweden. Many viewpoints share commonalities with those from other case studies (e.g., AT_F2, ES_F2, SE_F2, CH_F3 all focus on economic aspects of soil management); some combine multiple aspects that elsewhere appear distinct (e.g., SE_F2 prioritizes economic aspects as well as joy at work and practical work); and few are case-specific (e.g., DK_F2, which focuses on society and the local neighbourhood).

4.3. Second-order analysis

The second-order analysis resulted in a three-factor solution. The third factor is bipolar (i.e., comprises positive and negative loadings; see Watts and Stenner, 2012) and hence split into factors FO3a and FO3b. All first-order factors load onto a single second-order factor. Together, all factors account for 90% of the first-order factors' variance. For full results please refer to Appendix C; below we briefly summarize main results.

The first factor, FO1, groups 8 of the 15 first-order factors. The resulting viewpoint focuses on the environment and soil health, and preserving the soil for the future. Producing food is also relatively important for FO1, as are attitudes and values in general. Short-term thinking is rejected, and economic aspects as well as the institutional context are of comparatively low importance. The second factor, FO2, groups 4 first-order factors. The resulting viewpoint focuses on economic aspects of farming, which includes maximizing yields both short- and long-term. FO2 further cherishes independence, reflected, e.g., in the low importance of society and farm(er) context. The third factor, FO3a, groups 2 first-order factors, both from the Danish case study. The resulting viewpoint carefully considers the impacts of their actions on the local community, neighbourhood, and environment, giving special importance to societal aspects. FO3a farmers strive to enjoy their work as farmers, including the time spent doing practical work and using machinery. The fourth factor, FO3b, comprises only one first-order factor, CH_F3. It is hence identical to it. The corresponding viewpoint is distinct from others in its focus on risk-reduction through soil management, which includes the use of subsidies. It generally gives higher priority to the institutional context and to (existing) knowledge and experience than others. Environmental aspects and enjoying the work with the soil are unimportant for FO3b.

There are three consensus statements: Knowing a plot's soil quality data is ranked at zero by all factors (28: 0); as are practical experiences (14: 1, 0, 0, 1); and doing what one believes in is ranked between 0 and +3 but statistically similarly (15: +1, +2, +3, 0).

4.4. Result comparison

The results of the three analyses largely align. Most aspects that define a viewpoint according to one of the methods also define one or more viewpoints in the other two. This includes soil health (FC1, FO1, AT_F3, DK_F1, ES_F1, SE_F1, CH_F1), farm economics (FC2, FO2, AT_F2, ES_F2, SE_F2), the local community and environment (FC3, FO3a, DK_F2), and risk aversion (FC5, FO3b, ES_F2, CH_F3). Few aspects, such as the priority given to a traditional, productivist farming lifestyle (FC4, AT_F1, SE_F3, CH_F2), appear prominent in the results from only one or two approaches.

Fig. 8 visualises the congruence between methods by showing interview participants' allocation to viewpoints. It shows, for example, that FC1 largely corresponds to FO1, as most participants that load onto FC1 (purple lines) are also found in FO1, with very few exceptions. Similarly, FC2 (blue) largely corresponds to FO2, and FC3 (turquoise)

mostly to FO3a. The group of participants associated with FC4 in the composite analysis (green) all but one become part of FO1 in the second-order analysis, and those associated with FC5 (yellow) become part of FO2 and FO3b.

The composite analysis reveals differences and commonalities within and between case studies that remain hidden in the first- and second-order analyses: It shows within-case differences by grouping between-case commonalities that 'allow' participants from different regions to form a viewpoint even if they are the only ones sharing a particular nuance in their region (see FC4 and FC5). It shows between-case differences and commonalities as it shows that some of the composite viewpoints are formed only by participants from some regions (FC3), but many are not. However, more farmers drop out in the composite analysis compared to the other methods, as they fail to load significantly on only one factor. Instead, these participants mostly load on two factors, indicating that they do not share a single of the composite viewpoints.

The first-order, i.e., case-specific, results are more nuanced than the more aggregated composite and second-order analyses due to the greater diversity of viewpoints identified. This allows for more participants to remain in the typology. The first-order analysis results also show within-case differences, as we identify three distinct viewpoints in each region. The second-order analysis then highlights between-case commonalities among the within-case differences through the grouping.

5. Discussion and conclusions

5.1. Archetypal viewpoints on soil management

This paper first aimed to identify and describe archetypal viewpoints on soil management among cropland farmers from five different European regions. The interviewed farmers hold views about their work with the soil that can be grouped into 4–5 viewpoints. One focuses on soil health and the environment, one on economic aspects, one on the local community, and one is risk-averse. Depending on the method used, we additionally identify a viewpoint that highlights a traditional farming lifestyle, focusing on practical work and producing food. The first-order (region-specific) analysis provides additional nuances among viewpoints, such as open-mindedness or a focus on complying with regulations.

The viewpoints generally resemble some farmer types described in previous studies, showing that several general tendencies appear across regions and topics⁴: Our *Soil farmers* (viewpoint FC1) resemble *Environmentalists* or *Conservationists* (Bartkowski et al., 2022; Davies and Hodge, 2007). Due to the focus of our study, FC1 is distinct in its focus on soil health that complements its pro-environmental or conservationist attitude that other studies identify (e.g., Davies and Hodge, 2007; Khurajam et al., 2025; Walder and Kantelhardt, 2018). The *Economic farmers* (FC2) are in line with *Productivists* who focus on economic outcomes and yields (Bartkowski et al., 2022). In soil management, FC2 stresses functional aspects of soil health such as water retention capacity. Most distinct from previously identified farmer types is FC3, the *Sustainability farmers*. The priority they give to society and the neighbourhood is rare (but see Brodt et al., 2006; Happel et al., 2022). *Practical farmers* (FC4) are similar to some lifestyle-focused farmer types (Maybery et al., 2005) that uphold traditional productivist values and prioritize food production (see also Braitto et al., 2020; Davies and Hodge, 2007). The *Risk-avoiding farmers* (FC5) share many aspects with the *economic farmers* and thus the *Productivists* but are distinct in their focus on minimizing financial and agronomic risks. Risk aversion is a well-known driver of farmers' behaviour (Dessart et al., 2019) but to date rarely appears in farmer typologies.

⁴ We focus only on the viewpoints from the composite analysis here, since the others largely overlap.

5.2. The viewpoints in context

The second aim of our study was to investigate the context-dependency of farmers' viewpoints. We consider the regional context (comprising biophysical, societal, and cultural aspects), the biophysical context, and farm structural aspects (i.e., the farm context) and their relation to the viewpoints.

If viewpoints were strongly determined by the regional context, we would expect that participants' association with the composite analysis-viewpoints aligns closely with case study regions. This is not the case: Viewpoint FC1 is defined by farmers from all regions, FC2, FC4, and FC5 are defined by farmers from three regions each, and FC3 is defined by farmers from the Danish and Swedish case studies. This indicates that the relevance that farmers give to soil health, and, to a smaller extent, farm economics, a traditional farming lifestyle, and risk-aversion is rather independent of the regional context, as the related viewpoints co-exist in most regions. The economic-focused viewpoint FC2 is most prominent among the Spanish participants. This could be a result of the climatic and economic situation of these farmers, who had experienced two years of drought prior to the interviews that threatened their farms' economic viability. The importance of the local community appears more specific to the Danish and Swedish case studies, perhaps expressing cultural or political differences between Nordic countries and the rest of Europe. These results are stable across methods: Viewpoint FO1 groups first-order viewpoints from all case studies, demonstrating that farmers who prioritize soil health exist in all regions. The economics-focused viewpoints FO2 and FO3b group farmers from most, but not all regions, and again with Spanish farmers being represented more prominently than others. The society-focused viewpoint FO3a is defined by Danish farmers only, indicating that the regional societal and cultural context can influence viewpoints in some cases.

Concerning the biophysical context, the priority given to mitigating extreme weather events and to protecting water resources varies greatly across viewpoints but appears unrelated to case study regions. The relative importance of preventing soil erosion and increasing water retention capacity do seem related to regions and climatic conditions: Viewpoint FC3 is the only one to consider erosion prevention as unimportant and is defined by farmers from the Danish and Swedish case studies only, where topography limits erosion risks. Viewpoint FC2 considers soil water retention as essential and is mostly defined by farmers from the Spanish case study, where droughts are a major concern. Other participants who load significantly onto this factor also reported water shortages. However, the opposite conclusion is not valid: Not all farmers with land that is not prone to erosion load onto FC3, and not all those who experience drought onto FC2. The biophysical context, therefore, does not fully determine the viewpoints that farmers hold.

Farm structure provides the context for decision-making and could influence farmers' viewpoints, too. If this were the case, we would expect substantial differences in farm structural variables across viewpoints in Table 4, as farmers operating certain types of farms (e.g., those with livestock or part-time farmers) would prioritize different statements. We note some such differences: Farmers sharing the economically focused viewpoint FC2 tend to have the largest and mostly conventional farms, no livestock, and a relatively high level of agricultural education. Farmers sharing the risk-averse FC5 tend to have small farms with a large share of rented land. They tend to be youngest, while the traditionally minded FC4 farmers are, on average, oldest. Farms that hold livestock are likely to share the 'social' viewpoint FC3, and (partly) organic farmers tend to hold FC1 or FC3. However, these are not definite rules, e.g., not all participants who manage (very) large farms are

associated with FC2, farmers with organic farms are found in each viewpoint, as are farmers with university education or part-time farmers. We note that it is difficult to separate this from the regional context, as the structure of agriculture differs across case studies. The small number of defining farmers for some viewpoints must further caution the reader to draw quantitative conclusions.

We conclude that, according to our results, the regional, biophysical, and farm structural contexts relate to viewpoints to some extent, but by no means fully. As the major viewpoints are all shared by farmers from multiple or all regions and with diverse backgrounds, they must be independent of context to a substantial extent. This is in line with previous studies involving multiple regions (cf. Barnes et al., 2022; Casagrande et al., 2016; Gorton et al., 2008). However, as we outline in section 5.4, additional research on the interplay between farm context and farmer viewpoints is needed.

5.3. Policy conclusions

The mere recognition that farmers' viewpoints and priorities vary—independent of farm structural characteristics—implies that a diverse bundle of policies and communication strategies is needed to appeal to all farmers and, e.g., foster behavioural change (Klebl et al., 2024; Pedersen et al., 2020). Concrete farmer typologies like ours identify the aspects of farming that each viewpoint or type considers desirable or 'good' (Blackstock et al., 2010). Information can then be framed and policies designed in line with these aspects (Huber et al., 2024; Lyle, 2015; Oberlack et al., 2023). For example, promoting the uptake of sustainable soil management practices by highlighting their benefits for soil health may resonate with farmers sharing a soil health-centred viewpoint such as FC1. Farmers sharing an economically focused viewpoint like FC2 may instead prefer information on financial benefits such as reduced input use or new market opportunities. Community-focused farmers such as FC3 might respond to messages emphasizing societal or local community needs and benefits, and so forth. Social media offer an opportunity to disseminate such targeted information through farm influencers and communities (Rust et al., 2022; Witzling et al., 2023) that typically comprise farmers sharing common values and goals (Calvignac et al., 2025). Other actors in agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS) that are relevant sources of information for farmers (Fielke et al., 2020; Knierim et al., 2015; Sutherland and Labarthe, 2022) should also be aware of the diversity of viewpoints among farmers and the most prevalent ones, allowing them to tailor advice and support (Klerkx et al., 2017; Stråte et al., 2025).

Similarly, in terms of agricultural policies, economic incentives may motivate economically minded or risk-averse farmers to implement a new practice. However, payments may not be enough to convince, e.g., a traditional farmer who focuses on food production if a practice reduces yields (Dessart et al., 2019). A transformation of traditional farming values towards post-productivism may be needed to shift their practices, requiring different types of policies such as community work (Braitto et al., 2020). Cautious farmers concerned about economic or agronomic risks may respond to risk-management tools like insurance schemes, and yet others may benefit most from trainings and educational measures. However, tailoring policies to farmer types must consider issues of acceptance and fairness (Huber et al., 2024). Using a mix of information channels, framings, and policy measures that are accessible to all is likely the best option (Klebl et al., 2024; Pedersen et al., 2020).

Given our finding that farmers' viewpoints are largely universal across regions, such tailored communication strategies or policies could be developed and disseminated at supranational or -regional (e.g., EU or

federal level) and refined for national or regional use. This aligns well with current policy making such as the CAP as well as with the globalization of AKIS and farmers' information seeking behaviour (Fielke et al., 2020; Klerkx et al., 2017).

5.4. Methodological conclusions, limitations, and outlook

Using different approaches for analysing a multi-regional Q-Methodology study has generated interesting insights. First, the different approaches led to similar results in terms of content, emphasizing their robustness. Second, it shows benefits and drawbacks of each approach. The composite analysis resulted in more than a fourth of participants not loading onto a single factor, indicating that a substantial number of farmers share more than one of the identified viewpoints and the resulting types may be less distinct than desired. This was not the case for the first- and second-order analyses (although we note that a particularly large share of the Swedish participants were non-loaders also in the first- and second-order analyses; we do not know why this was the case). On the other hand, the composite analysis identified the 'Practical farmer' viewpoint as a distinct type, which did not appear in the other analyses, and it can help to identify differences and commonalities within and between regions. Future users of these approaches should be aware of methodological differences and carefully consider which outcome—greater inclusivity and distinctness of viewpoints or the identification of rare types and differences across cases. More studies comparing the different approaches are needed to draw conclusions about their respective benefits and shortcomings.

While we consider a multi-regional Q-Methodology study very well-suited to address our first research aim, it proved more difficult to address our second research aim in this manner. The largely qualitative nature of Q-Methodology and the correspondingly limited sample size make it difficult to discern definite relationships between contextual factors and the identified viewpoints, not least because the contextual factors are many and of a complex nature (e.g., cultural aspects). Different research approaches, e.g., large-scale quantitative surveys or more in-depth qualitative approaches (including follow-up post-Q interviews), are needed here. Moreover, even if relationships between contextual factors and viewpoints exist, the direction of causality is not clear. For example, farm structure might influence viewpoints, but viewpoints can affect the structure of a farm, as, e.g., economically minded farmers might be keener than others to grow their business. Longitudinal research or experimental research that investigates farmer viewpoints and farm structural developments (e.g., after farm takeover or succession) are needed to investigate this. We further note that some contextual factors could influence viewpoints in ways that a Q-Methodology study cannot easily capture. For example, farmers might have different priorities on rented or owned land and thus would rank statements differently when thinking only about one of these ownership types. Since no instructions were given to participants in this respect, we do not know which type of land part-tenants had in mind during the sorting. Farmers with livestock and those without may also have different priorities in soil management. Additional analyses (e.g., separate first-order analyses for these two types of farms) could provide insights into this question but are left for future research.

While a benefit of our study is the inclusion of several case studies, this also added complexity to the analysis. The case study regions differ

in many respects, including the biophysical context, culture, and farm structures. Our strategies to contact participants—and hence the composition of our samples—also differed, as did the interviewers and interview languages. The structured and standardized interview process of Q-Methodology, our participant selection process, and the analysis methods aimed to alleviate these problems. Since our results show that viewpoints correspond to case study regions only to a limited extent, we believe that no great bias arises at the case study level. We partly had to rely on convenience sampling in some case studies (e.g., open calls for participation in newsletters in Switzerland; approaching farmers at the local advisory centre in Spain). Our P-sample may thus be biased towards farmers interested in (sustainable) soil management as these are more likely to respond to such calls. Purposive snowball sampling aimed to alleviate this. Moreover, women (and potentially other minority groups of farmers) are underrepresented in our sample when compared to official statistics, which may also bias our results and limits our understanding of how gender relates to viewpoints. This underlines that—as is the case for any Q-Methodological study—no quantitative conclusions about the prevalence of different viewpoints must be made; we can merely affirm their existence.

Confirming our viewpoint narratives by means of post-Q interviews with highly-loading participants (Webler et al., 2009) would have strengthened our results and is highly recommended for future studies. Such interviews could also be used to develop targeted policy support measures attractive to the respective farmer types. To study the prevalence of different viewpoints and to investigate their relationship to behavioural outcomes, large-scale surveys would be valuable. This could also extend our research to (other European) regions not covered here, notably Eastern Europe. Understanding how viewpoints evolve over time under changing farm structural, environmental and policy conditions would also be valuable.

Declaration of generative AI and AI assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used OpenAI's ChatGPT-4 Turbo (December 2024 version) to shorten selected paragraphs in the introduction and discussion sections. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the text as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Heidi Leonhardt: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Michael Brait:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nicole Bütikofer:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Morten Graversgaard:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marion Hacek:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Investigation, Data curation. **Jenny Höckert:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Ernesto Lunar-Koch:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Christina**

Lundström: Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mariella Schreiber:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Mette Tiselius:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Data curation.

Funding

This research was supported by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme (grant no. 862695).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

We thank the farmers and stakeholders who participated in the interviews for their time and insights. We are grateful to those who helped us to get in touch with farmers: Marta Goberna and the farmers' association APAG in Spain, Hermann Dommaier-Bachl in Austria, Line Ditlev in Denmark. Thanks also to Olivier Heller and Annelie Holzkämper for support in gathering additional information about the Swiss case study.

The first-order results of the Austrian and the Swiss case studies were also published as Master Theses, see [Bütikofer \(2023\)](#) and [Lunar-Koch \(2024\)](#).

Appendix A. Q-set

Table A.1

List of statements comprising the Q-set, main sources, and statement categories.

No.	Statement	Source	Category
1	... that my plots look tidy and neat.	Braito et al., 2020 ; Dessart et al., 2019	Attitude/Values
2	... to preserve the soil for future generations.	Braito et al., 2020 , Stakeholders/project team	Attitude/Values
3	... to consider the costs involved.	Happel et al., 2022 ; Lu et al., 2022	Economics
4	... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	Braito et al., 2020	Economics
5	... to prioritize short-term profit	Prokopy et al., 2019 ; Serebrennikov et al., 2020	Economics
6	... to receive subsidies for what I do.	Braito et al., 2020 ; Reimer et al., 2014 ; Serebrennikov et al., 2020	Institutional context
7	... to maximize crop yields in this year.	Lu et al., 2022 , Prokopy et al., 2019	Economics
8	... how far a plot is away from the farm house.	Braito et al., 2020 ; Foguesatto et al., 2020	Farm(er) context
9	... to hand it over to my successors in a good condition.	Cullen et al., 2020 ; Prokopy et al., 2008 ; Stakeholders/project team	Farm(er) context
10	... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	Foguesatto et al., 2020 , Prokopy et al., 2019 ; Stakeholders/project team	Farm(er) context
11	... to make a difference between the land I own and the land I do not own myself.	Braito et al., 2020 , Lu et al., 2022 , Prokopy et al., 2019	Farm(er) context
12	... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	Braito et al., 2020 , Foguesatto et al., 2020 , Prokopy et al., 2019	Knowledge and experience
13	... to rely on the experiences of colleagues.	Braito et al., 2020 ; Happel et al., 2022 ; Ranjan et al., 2019	Knowledge and experience
14	... to rely on my own practical experiences.	Happel et al., 2022 ; Lu et al., 2022 ; Prokopy et al., 2019 ; Ranjan et al., 2019	Knowledge and experience
15	... to do what I believe in.	Bartkowski and Bartke, 2018 ; Mills et al., 2017	Attitude/Values
16	... to consider how neighbouring plots are farmed.	Braito et al., 2020 ; Dessart et al., 2019 ; Happel et al., 2022 ; Mills et al., 2017	Farm(er) context
17	... to consider how my actions impact my neighbourhood.	Braito et al., 2020	Society
18	... to minimize working time.	Braito et al., 2020	Economics
19	... to rely on traditional, handed-down knowledge.	Braito et al., 2020 , Happel et al., 2022	Knowledge and experience
20	... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	Braito et al., 2020 , Happel et al., 2022 , Serebrennikov et al., 2020	Knowledge and experience
21	... how long I will continue to farm.	Serebrennikov et al., 2020 , Prokopy et al., 2008	Farm(er) context
22	... that I don't have to deal with more bureaucracy than necessary.	Ranjan et al., 2019	Institutional context
23	... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	Braito et al., 2020 , Happel et al., 2022 , Lu et al., 2022	Knowledge and experience
24	... not to come in conflict with legal regulations.	Braito et al., 2020 , Happel et al., 2022 ; Stakeholders/project team	Institutional context
25	... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather events.	Stakeholders/project team	Environment and soil
26	... to reduce soil erosion.	Stakeholders/project team	Environment and soil
27	... to prevent pests.	Stakeholders/project team	Environment and soil
28	... to know the plot's soil quality data.	Prokopy et al., 2019	Knowledge and experience
29	... to meet the requirements of my buyers.	Serebrennikov et al., 2020	Society
30	... to meet the expectations of society.	Braito et al., 2020 , Serebrennikov et al., 2020	Society

(continued on next page)

Table A.1 (continued)

When I work with my soil, it is important for me ...			
No.	Statement	Source	Category
31	... to produce food for society.	Braitto et al., 2020; Cullen et al., 2020	Society
32	... how my actions impact the environment.	Braitto et al., 2020; Cullen et al., 2020; Lu et al., 2022; Prokopy et al., 2008, 2019	Environment and soil
33	... that I work together with nature.	Dessart et al., 2019, Prokopy et al., 2019	Attitude/Values
34	... how my actions impact soil organisms such as earthworms.	Braitto et al., 2020	Environment and soil
35	... how others perceive my actions.	Braitto et al., 2020	Society
36	... that the work gives me pleasure.	Braitto et al., 2020, Cullen et al., 2020	Attitude/Values
37	... to avoid economic risks.	Braitto et al., 2020, Happel et al., 2022, Prokopy et al., 2019, Serebrennikov et al., 2020	Economics
38	... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	Braitto et al., 2020	Economics
39	... that I try new practices.	Braitto et al., 2020, Cullen et al., 2020, Happel et al., 2022, Ranjan et al., 2019	Attitude/Values
40	... to increase organic matter.	Stakeholders/project team	Environment and soil
41	... to prevent nutrient losses.	Prokopy et al., 2019	Environment and soil
42	... to minimize machinery use.	Stakeholders/project team	Economics
43	...to protect water resources.	Stakeholders/project team	Environment and soil
44	...to consider climatic changes.	Stakeholders/project team	Environment and soil
45	...to increase the soil's water retention capacity.	Stakeholders/project team	Environment and soil

References for Appendix A

- Bartkowski, B., & Bartke, S. (2018). Leverage Points for Governing Agricultural Soils: A Review of Empirical Studies of European Farmers' Decision-Making. *Sustainability*, 10(9), 3179. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su10093179>
- Braitto, M., Leonhardt, H., Penker, M., Schauppenlehner-Kloyber, E., Thaler, G., & Flint, C. G. (2020). The plurality of farmers' views on soil management calls for a policy mix. *Land Use Policy*, 99(November 2019), 104876. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104876>
- Cullen, P., Ryan, M., O'Donoghue, C., Hynes, S., hUallacháin, D. Ó., & Sheridan, H. (2020). Impact of farmer self-identity and attitudes on participation in agri-environment schemes. *Land Use Policy*, 95, 104660. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104660>
- Dessart, F. J., Barreiro-Hurlé, J., & Van Bavel, R. (2019). Behavioural factors affecting the adoption of sustainable farming practices: A policy-oriented review. *European Review of Agricultural Economics*, 46(3), 417–471. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbz019>
- Foguesatto, C. R., Borges, J. A. R., & Machado, J. A. D. (2020). A review and some reflections on farmers' adoption of sustainable agricultural practices worldwide. *Science of The Total Environment*, 729, 138831. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138831>
- Happel, M., Orsi, F., Hartmann, T., & Bakker, M. (2022). Fertile ground, complex matter: Plurality of farmers' attitudes towards green waste application as sustainable soil management. *Sociologia Ruralis*, 62(3), 509–541. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/soru.12381>
- Lu, J., Ranjan, P., Floress, K., Arbuckle, J. G., Church, S. P., Eanes, F. R., Gao, Y., Gramig, B. M., Singh, A. S., & Prokopy, L. S. (2022). A meta-analysis of agricultural conservation intentions, behaviors, and practices: Insights from 35 years of quantitative literature in the United States. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 323, 116240. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116240>
- Mills, J., Gaskell, P., Ingram, J., Dwyer, J., Reed, M., & Short, C. (2017). Engaging farmers in environmental management through a better understanding of behaviour. *Agriculture and Human Values*, 34(2), 283–299. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-016-9705-4>
- Prokopy, L. S., Floress, K., Arbuckle, J. G., Church, S. P., Eanes, F. R., Gao, Y., Gramig, B. M., Ranjan, P., & Singh, A. S. (2019). Adoption of agricultural conservation practices in the United States: Evidence from 35 years of quantitative literature. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 74(5), 520–534. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.74.5.520>
- Prokopy, L. S., Floress, K., Klotthor-Weinkauff, D., & Baumgart-Getz, A. (2008). Determinants of agricultural best management practice adoption: Evidence from the literature. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 63(5), 300–311. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.63.5.300>
- Ranjan, P., Church, S. P., Floress, K., & Prokopy, L. S. (2019). Synthesizing Conservation Motivations and Barriers: What Have We Learned from Qualitative Studies of Farmers' Behaviors in the United States? *Society & Natural Resources*, 32(11), 1171–1199. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2019.1648710>
- Reimer, A., Thompson, A., Prokopy, L. S., Arbuckle, J. G., Genskow, K., Jackson-Smith, D., Lynne, G., McCann, L., Morton, L. W., & Nowak, P. (2014). People, place, behavior, and context: A research agenda for expanding our understanding of what motivates farmers' conservation behaviors. *Journal of Soil and Water Conservation*, 69(2), 57A-61A. doi:<https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.69.2.57A>
- Serebrennikov, D., Thorne, F., Kallas, Z., & McCarthy, S. N. (2020). Factors Influencing Adoption of Sustainable Farming Practices in Europe: A Systemic Review of Empirical Literature. *Sustainability*, 12(22), 9719. doi:<https://doi.org/10.3390/su12229719>

Appendix B. Composite analysis: additional results

Participants' association with each factor

Cells highlighted in yellow indicate significant association with a factor; values reflect the degree of association (correlation). Participants highlighted in orange do not load significantly on any single factor.

Table C.6

Interview participants' association with factors in the composite analysis.

Q-sort	FC1	FC2	FC3	FC4	FC5
AT01	0.7951	0.256	0.2491	-0.0611	0.2379
AT02	0.3436	0.1467	0.1352	0.2946	0.4769
AT03	0.6284	0.3321	0.0968	-0.0266	0.2254
AT04	0.1974	0.289	0.2531	0.122	0.589
AT05	0.7197	0.2839	0.1533	-0.0775	0.1862
AT06_1	0.713	-0.0664	0.2784	0.2059	0.0519
AT06_2	0.5443	0.147	0.1557	0.3152	0.0253
AT07	0.5165	0.1694	0.0425	0.3467	-0.108
AT08	0.6947	0.2567	0.3073	0.0652	-0.1526
AT09	0.6119	-0.0215	0.1643	0.0455	0.3595
AT10	0.853	0.0713	0.1341	0.2023	0.1265
AT11	0.604	0.286	0.1471	0.0612	0.3362
AT12	0.7398	0.2017	-0.0987	-0.055	0.2896
AT13	0.846	0.0501	0.0918	0.0957	0.0902
AT14	0.7383	-0.1316	0.1975	0.075	0.1508
AT15	0.5793	0.1426	-0.0016	0.183	-0.0608
AT16	0.4642	0.4218	0.2922	0.1412	0.4489
AT17	0.7027	-0.0153	0.2807	0.0314	-0.063
AT18	0.4847	0.2012	0.0828	0.228	-0.0013
AT19	0.4894	-0.0515	0.0672	-0.0367	0.2798
AT20	-0.1596	0.4221	0.1236	0.2136	0.1688
AT21	0.5529	0.2107	0.1146	0.2177	0.2184
AT22	0.6228	0.1139	0.1808	0.3313	0.172
AT23	0.5202	0.3646	0.3035	-0.0508	0.293
AT24	0.7677	0.1448	0.0722	0.2179	0.3368
AT25	0.6795	0.0271	0.1667	0.2229	-0.1493
AT26	0.5459	0.4448	0.3154	0.0816	0.2322
AT27	0.7243	0.1183	0.1015	0.0874	0.3794
AT28	0.5152	0.2948	0.0381	0.3479	0.1708
AT29	0.337	0.4618	0.0918	0.1332	0.0949
AT30	0.579	0.2616	0.2727	-0.2255	0.3428
CH01	0.5748	0.0382	0.3961	0.3495	-0.0173
CH02	0.8206	0.1184	0.1422	0.1162	0.2368
CH04	0.7872	0.0579	0.1554	0.1937	0.0753
CH05	0.5683	0.3711	0.1117	0.098	-0.1186
CH06	0.0939	0.0105	-0.0461	0.1669	0.5229
CH07	0.7444	0.3343	0.1995	0.1381	0.2282
CH08	0.7958	0.1466	0.1148	0.1138	0.012
CH09	0.7682	0.0691	0.3188	0.1852	-0.0734
CH11	0.6894	0.162	0.301	0.0873	-0.1117
CH12	0.4071	0.1062	0.2833	0.5796	0.2339
CH13	0.818	0.195	0.1054	0.1228	0.0106
CH14	0.4451	0.4242	0.0984	0.1746	0.071
CH15	0.7407	0.1041	0.0783	-0.0283	0.0577
CH16	0.6606	0.1296	0.1229	0.1997	-0.0913
CH17	0.1173	0.1392	0.0058	0.3897	0.0621
CH18	0.8071	0.086	0.3301	0.0642	0.0835
CH19	0.7831	0.1146	0.2353	0.0382	0.017
CH20	0.7398	0.2769	0.2037	0.1111	0.2023
CH21	0.7322	0.0374	0.3329	-0.0254	0.1715
CH23	0.5742	0.1158	0.3327	0.2827	0.2517
CH24	0.5599	0.1334	0.2955	0.2918	0.1074
CH25	0.8167	0.0101	0.0799	0.1527	0.2371
CH26	0.6085	0.0545	0.2356	0.1337	0.3135
DK01	0.2615	0.2219	-0.0032	0.195	-0.1377
DK02	-0.0657	0.1558	0.4334	-0.0874	-0.1098
DK03	0.3532	-0.4233	0.6195	-0.0488	0.0563
DK04	0.3	-0.0055	0.5985	-0.2782	-0.0819
DK05	0.2536	-0.1833	0.6139	0.1562	0.013
DK06	0.3867	0.1356	0.441	0.0673	0.2553
DK07	0.0691	-0.1124	0.6299	-0.0061	-0.2451
DK08	0.1177	0.0511	0.583	0.1207	0.0842
DK09	0.1881	0.053	0.5975	0.1585	0.0619
DK10	0.7292	0.1232	0.4257	0.0406	-0.0218
DK11	0.3276	0.4216	0.2292	0.1637	-0.284
DK12	0.5349	0.2881	0.5272	-0.2946	0.1284
DK13	0.3857	0.1298	0.5536	-0.0903	-0.0173
DK14	0.7098	0.2575	0.3444	0.1789	-0.0411
DK15	0.6884	0.1563	0.3671	0.0795	-0.1375
DK16	0.4971	0.6226	0.3828	-0.0306	-0.0376
DK17	0.5791	0.1685	0.4897	0.1032	0.1782
DK18	0.6151	0.3053	0.3636	0.0492	-0.0673
DK19	0.555	0.1973	0.3915	0.1224	0.1337
DK20	0.5409	0.4142	0.4473	0.0195	0.0982

ES01	0.5047	0.6909	0.1441	-0.1542	0.0774
ES02	0.5222	0.4158	0.0253	0.1896	-0.2345
ES03	0.4853	0.3637	-0.1341	-0.0669	0.2198
ES04	0.4235	0.553	-0.1658	-0.0534	0.1155
ES05	0.04	0.4849	-0.0661	0.2314	0.0608
ES06	0.1118	0.1609	0.1604	0.3224	0.2472
ES07	-0.172	0.3346	0.355	-0.0524	0.3764
ES08	0.2063	0.4389	-0.0252	0.2324	0.021
ES09	0.2512	0.4347	0.2007	-0.0011	-0.0153
ES10	-0.1512	0.6429	0.1789	-0.333	0.1912
ES11	0.2198	0.5176	0.0361	-0.0491	0.3682
ES12	0.2622	0.578	-0.0112	0.2061	0.2139
ES13	0.0105	0.0314	0.0301	-0.1723	-0.0384
ES14	0.4258	0.3441	0.0349	0.364	-0.0404
ES15	0.1858	0.4026	-0.0219	0.5042	0.0838
ES16	-0.2144	0.528	-0.086	0.4491	0.1886
ES17	0.4747	-0.0298	0.0992	-0.0595	0.385
ES18	0.6546	0.216	0.0444	0.2628	0.1532
ES19	0.3496	0.5357	0.0932	0.3916	0.1996
ES20	0.4315	0.1803	-0.1208	0.2496	0.2823
ES21	-0.1564	0.6227	0.1878	-0.2687	0.2303
ES22	-0.0158	0.3582	-0.0588	0.1284	0.4026
ES23	0.4244	0.3758	-0.0398	0.2539	0.2918
SE01	0.3092	0.1745	0.3093	0.4685	-0.0579
SE02	0.4935	-0.07	0.4911	0.4741	-0.0069
SE03	0.0488	0.4948	0.2923	0.3283	-0.0761
SE04	0.403	0.1511	0.5684	-0.0608	0.0476
SE05	0.7919	0.1568	0.2541	0.1829	0.0001
SE06	0.3097	-0.0045	0.1183	0.3481	0.1363
SE07	0.1324	0.5679	0.452	0.222	-0.0866
SE08	0.5015	0.1772	0.3728	0.4816	-0.2951
SE09	0.1703	0.2042	0.2743	0.5639	0.3514
SE11	0.2782	0.2676	0.6871	0.129	0.1412
SE12	0.7814	-0.0551	0.252	0.2338	-0.0286
SE13	0.1979	0.1976	0.3612	0.3275	0.3789
SE14	0.2696	0.1423	0.6247	0.3583	0.2212
SE15	0.4141	0.3689	0.5104	0.3125	0.1187
SE16	0.6602	-0.0477	0.3446	0.3174	-0.1004
SE17	0.6464	0.1163	0.3689	0.3328	-0.1021
SE18	0.2828	0.064	0.418	0.5424	-0.2199
SE19	0.4326	0.1852	0.4268	0.3101	0.3745
SE20	0.4397	0.0211	0.5019	0.3855	0.2552
SE21	0.3727	0.5634	0.3482	0.0382	-0.0418
SE22	0.3631	0.3551	0.418	0.2869	0.1891
SE23	0.3463	0.2032	0.4179	0.4173	0.0953
SE24	-0.042	0.1873	0.523	0.2913	-0.0211
SE25	0.587	0.4802	0.4564	-0.0012	0.0949
SE26	0.1791	0.2685	0.6228	0.0344	0.2731
SE27	-0.2473	0.2669	0.4431	0.3715	0.0734
SE28	0.1129	0.681	0.3015	0.2709	-0.072
SE29	0.5117	0.2295	0.5378	0.2607	0.2624
SE30	0.2817	0.0963	0.5227	0.4522	0.087
SE31	0.1755	0.034	0.654	-0.009	0.1727
SE32	0.5686	0.0393	0.5432	0.0525	0.151
SE33	0.2546	0.3327	0.4947	0.1891	0.4293

Salience analysis results

Normalized z-scores were calculated by summing the z-scores of all statements belonging to one category and normalizing them for the number of statements (by dividing the sum by the number) per factor.

Statement category	N statements	Norm. z-score FC1	Norm. z-score FC2	Norm. z-score FC3	Norm. z-score FC4	Norm. z-score FC5
Attitude/values	6	0.64	0.27	0.69	0.72	0.03
Economics	8	-0.33	1.09	0.31	-0.12	0.89
Environment & soil	10	0.96	0.53	-0.05	0.04	-0.02
Farm(er) context	6	-0.81	-0.72	-0.63	-0.54	-0.86
Institutional context	3	-0.75	-0.75	-0.25	0.66	0.37
Knowledge & experience	7	-0.11	-0.50	-0.30	0.35	-0.23
Society	5	-0.57	-1.13	0.09	-0.98	-0.27

Appendix C. Second-order analysis results

Statements and associated rankings by factor

Table E.1
Statements and statement rankings by factor for the second-order analysis.

No.	Statement	FO1	FO2	F3Oa	FO3b
1	... that my plots look tidy and neat.	-2	1	-3	3
2	... to preserve the soil for future generations.	4	0	3	1
3	... to consider the costs involved.	0	3	1	3
4	... to ensure the long-term economic viability of my farm.	3	4	4	1
5	... to prioritize short-term profit	-4	3*	-4	-3
6	... to receive subsidies for what I do.	-2	-2	-3	3*
7	... to maximize crop yields in this year.	-2	3*	-1	-1
8	... how far a plot is away from the farm house.	-3	-3	2*	-3
9	... to hand it over to my successors in a good condition.	3	0	1	0
10	... that it is possible to work with the machines I have access to.	0	-1	-1	3*
11	... to make a difference between the land I own and the land I do not own.	-4	-2	-2	-4
12	... to rely on what I learned in my training or education.	-1	-1	-1	2*
13	... to rely on the experiences of colleagues.	-1	-2	0	0
14	... to rely on my own practical experiences.	1	0	0	1
15	... to do what I believe in.	1	2	3	0
16	... to consider how neighboring plots are farmed.	-3	-4	-4	-2
17	... to consider how my actions impact my neighbourhood.	-1	-2	4*	-1
18	... to minimize working time.	-1	2	-1	0
19	... to rely on traditional, handed-down knowledge.	-1	-1	-3	-3
20	... to rely on the advice from advisory services.	-1	0	0	-2
21	... how long I will continue to farm.	-3	-3	-2	-1
22	... that I don't have to deal with more bureaucracy than necessary.	-2	1	0	-4
23	... to rely on the latest recommendations from research.	0	-1	1	2
24	... not to come in conflict with legal regulations.	0	-1	0	1
25	... to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather events.	1	-1	-2	2
26	... to reduce soil erosion.	2	1	-1	1
27	... to prevent pests.	0	3	-3*	2
28	... to know the plot's soil quality data.	0	0	0	0
29	... to meet the requirements of my buyers.	-1	0	0	4*
30	... to meet the expectations of society.	-2	-3	1	-1
31	... to produce food for society.	1	0	-1	-1
32	... how my actions impact the environment.	2	0	3	0
33	... that I work together with nature.	3	-1	1	0
34	... how my actions impact soil organisms such as earthworms.	2*	0	-1	-2
35	... how others perceive my actions.	-3	-4	1*	-3
36	... that the work gives me pleasure.	3	2	3	-2*
37	... to avoid economic risks.	0*	2	2	4
38	... to ensure a stable yield in the long term.	2	4	2	1
39	... that I try new practices.	1	-3*	1	1
40	... to increase organic matter.	4*	1	0	0
41	... to prevent nutrient losses.	2	1	2	-1
42	... to minimize machinery use.	0	1	-2*	2
43	...to protect water resources.	1	2	2	-2*
44	...to consider climatic changes.	0	-2	0	0
45	...to increase the soil's water retention capacity.	1	1	-2	-1

Note: * indicates statements that are ranked statistically significantly different by this factor compared to all others. Italics indicates consensus statements that do not differ between any pair of factors.

First-order analysis viewpoints' association with each factor

Highlighted cells indicate significant association with a factor; values reflect the degree of association (correlation)

Table 7

Association of first-order factors with second-order factors (second-order analysis).

Q-sort	FO1	FO2	FO3a	FO3b
AT_F1	0.9147	0.0873	0.0223	-0.0223
AT_F2	0.3829	0.6175	-0.162	0.162
AT_F3	0.8137	0.341	-0.0884	0.0884
CH_F1	0.929	0.0991	0.0269	-0.0269
CH_F2	0.6983	0.1793	0.1929	-0.1929
CH_F3	0.3028	0.2189	-0.5158	0.5158
DK_F1	0.805	0.3555	0.2134	-0.2134
DK_F2	0.4954	-0.1054	0.673	-0.673
DK_F3	0.2883	0.3537	0.6466	-0.6466
ES_F1	0.7211	0.4227	-0.2037	0.2037
ES_F2	-0.0577	0.8579	-0.0482	0.0482
ES_F3	0.4701	0.4879	0.002	-0.002
SE_F1	0.8705	0.1615	0.276	-0.276
SE_F2	0.3358	0.7388	0.2177	-0.2177
SE_F3	0.6243	0.254	0.2056	-0.2056

Saliency analysis results

Normalized z-scores were calculated by summing the z-scores of all statements belonging to one category and normalizing them for the number of statements (by dividing the sum by the number) per factor.

Statement category	N statements	Norm. z-score FO1	Norm. z-score FO2	Norm. z-score FO3a	Norm. z-score FO3b
Attitude/values	6	0.81	0.06	0.61	0.24
Economics	8	-0.26	1.3	0.02	0.42
Environment & soil	10	0.82	0.29	-0.10	-0.05
Farm(er) context	6	-0.80	-1.10	-0.47	-0.56
Institutional context	3	-0.68	-0.27	-0.56	0
Knowledge & experience	7	-0.15	-0.34	-0.15	0
Society	5	-0.62	-0.79	0.52	-0.19

Consensus

Three statements show a very high agreement between all factors. These include knowing a plot's soil quality data, which is ranked at zero by all factors (28: 0; consensus), relying on own practical experiences which is equally indifferent to all (14: 1,0,0,1; consensus), and doing what one believes in, which is ranked between 0 and +3 but still statistically similarly (15: +1,+2,+3,0; consensus).

Other statements with consensus at a lower significance level that were ranked consistently at the negative side of the distribution include the consideration of neighbouring plots (16: -3,-4,-4,-2), relying on traditional knowledge (19: -1,-1,-3,-3), and the expected continuation of farming (21: -3,-3,-2,-1). All other consensus statements at this significance level tend to be arranged around the center of the Q sorting grid.

Narratives by factor

Viewpoint 2nd-order FO1

This factor groups 8 of the 15 viewpoints (representing 71 farmers in total) and captures 40% of the variance. It groups the first factor of each country in addition to AT_F3, CH_F2, and SE_F3. Considering these factors, it appears to capture all groups that have a focus on soil health and/or ecology as well as on future generations. In addition, it groups factors with a focus on food production. The topics ranked highest by this factor are "environment and soil" and "attitudes/values", "farm(er) context" and "institutional context" are ranked lowest.

The most important aspects of soil management for FO1 are preserving the soil for future generations, both in general (2: +4) as well as for farm successors (9: +3), and to increase the soil's organic matter (40*: +4). Other soil health aspects are also relatively important for FO2 (34*: +2; 41: +2, consensus with viewpoint FO3a; 26: +1 and 45: +1, consensus with viewpoint FO2), as is working together with nature (33: +3). Enjoying work (36: +3, consensus with viewpoint FO3a) and producing food for society (31: +1) are important aspects, too.

Of comparatively low importance are many of the business- and marketing-related aspects of soil management. Considering the costs of a practice (3: 0) and avoiding economic risks (37*: 0) are of lower relevance than for other viewpoints, as are buyers' requirements (29: -1) and minimizing working time (18: -1, consensus with viewpoint FO3a). Maximizing short-term yields is also of low importance (7: -2). Viewpoint FO1 agrees least with making a difference between owned and not-owned land (11: -4, consensus with viewpoint FO3b) and with prioritizing short-term profits (5: -4, consensus with viewpoint FO3a).

Overall, viewpoint FO1 focuses on soil health aspects with the motivation to preserve the soil for the future. Short-term thinking is, consequently, rejected and economic aspects are of comparatively low importance.

Viewpoint 2nd-order FO2

This factor groups 4 of the 15 viewpoints and covers 18% of the study variance. It represents 25 farmers in total. FO2 groups most of the viewpoints

that place business and economic aspects at the center of soil management strategies, including one focused on risk avoidance and others with a long-term focus or open-mindedness as a distinguishing characteristic. The most highly ranked topic is “economics”, while “farm(er) context” statements are ranked, on average, lowest.

The most important aspects for viewpoint FO2's soil management are ensuring long-term stability in terms of both economic viability (4: +4, consensus with viewpoint FO3a) and yields (38: +4). To achieve these long-term economic goals, maximizing short-term profits (5*: +3) and yields (7*: +3) is also very important. To do so, viewpoint FO2 carefully considers the costs of a practice (3: +3, consensus with viewpoint FO3b) and aims to minimize the work time needed (18: +2). Viewpoint FO2 also aims to prevent some environmental consequences through soil management, especially those that could impact the farm: preventing pests (27: +3), increasing the soil's water retention capacity (45: +1, consensus with viewpoint FO1), and protecting water resources in general (43: +2, consensus with viewpoint FO3a) are ranked as more important than by most other factors.

Preventing the soil for the future (2: 0, 9: 0, consensus with viewpoint FO3b) is not unimportant, but of decidedly lower relevance than for other factors; as is working together with nature (33: -1) and considering climatic changes (44: -2). Viewpoint FO2 is also not inclined to try new practices (39*: -3), and, in line with this, recommendations from research (23: -1) and learning from others' experiences (13: -2) are of low importance, too. Underlining the focus on independence from others, statements that refer to one's own influence on others (17: -2) and especially others' influence on one's own work (30: -3, 35: -4, 16: -4, consensus with viewpoint FO3a) are consistently ranked at the far negative side of the Q sorting grid.

In sum, this viewpoint places a decided focus on the economic aspects of farming, which also includes maximizing yields both short- and long-term. In this, viewpoint FO2 strives to be independent from others.

Viewpoint 2nd-order FO3a

This factor was part of the initially bipolar factor 3, indicating strong disagreement (i.e., partly opposite sortings) with factor FO3b. It groups 2 viewpoints, both from Denmark. It captures (together with FO3b) 10% of the study variance and groups 7 farmers in total. Both viewpoints grouped in this factor differ from all others by placing great relevance on the community and neighbourhood they work in. Correspondingly, the most highly ranked topics are “attitude/values” and “society”; statements relating to the “institutional context” are, on average, ranked lowest.

Similar to viewpoint FO2, viewpoint FO3a places great importance on the long-term economic viability of the farm (4: +4, consensus with viewpoint FO2). However, distinct from all others, FO3a also carefully evaluates how their actions impact the neighbourhood (17*: +4), considers society's expectations (30: +1) as well as others' perceptions of their actions (35*: +1) in their work. In addition, FO3a wishes to enjoy their work (36: +3, consensus with viewpoint FO1) and do what they believe in (15: +3, consensus). The importance placed on impacts on the surroundings also plays out for environmental impacts: Viewpoint FO3a considers it relatively important to protect water resources (43: +2, consensus with viewpoint FO2) and to prevent nutrient losses (41: +2, consensus with viewpoint FO1). Viewpoint FO3a is also the only viewpoint that considers the distance between a plot and the farmstead (8*: +2) as important for soil management.

Several soil preservation-related statements are comparatively unimportant for viewpoint FO3a, perhaps because they are not problematic in the region: increasing organic matter (40: 0, consensus with viewpoint FO3b), reducing soil erosion (26: -1), mitigating effects from extreme weather events (25: -2), or increasing the soil's water retention capacity (45: -2) are all ranked as neutral to unimportant. Minimizing production inputs such as labor (18: -1, consensus with viewpoint FO1) or machinery (42*: -2) are of low importance too, as is preventing pests through soil management (27*: -3). Viewpoint FO3a does not consider tidy and neat fields as important (1: -3), nor do the associated viewpoints want to receive subsidies for their actions (6: -3), and they do not consider how neighbouring plots are farmed (16: -4, consensus with viewpoint FO2). Of very low importance is generating a short-term profit (5: -4, consensus with viewpoint FO1).

In summary, viewpoint FO3a places greater importance than all others on the community they live in and carefully considers the impacts of their actions, including potential environmentally detrimental effects. Given this, farmers sharing viewpoint FO3a strive to enjoy their work as farmers, including the time spent with manual work and using machinery.

Viewpoint 2nd-order FO3b

This factor was part of the initially bipolar factor 3, indicating strong disagreement (i.e., partly opposite sortings) with factor FO3a. It comprises only one viewpoint, CH_F3, and is hence identical with it in terms of the Q-sorting. Since the factors it compares to are different, distinguishing elements partly differ, too. FO3b groups 2 farmers in total and, together with FO3a, covers 10% of the study variance. The topic ranked highest on average is “economics”, while “farm(er) context” statements are ranked lowest.

Viewpoint FO3b places great emphasis on farm economics, but with a pronounced focus on risk avoidance (37: +4). Important aspects thereof are meeting buyers' requirements (29*: +4), making use of subsidies (6: +3*), carefully considering the costs associated with a practice (3: +3, consensus with viewpoint FO2), using the machines already available on the farm (10*: +3), and minimizing machinery use (42: +2). Viewpoint FO3b also aims to mitigate negative effects from extreme weather events via their soil management (25: +2). Another relevant aspect for viewpoint FO3b is the appearance of their plots as tidy and neat (1: +3). More than others, viewpoint FO3b relies on their own training and education (12*: +2) and on recommendations from research (23: +2).

Compared to others, this factor is less concerned with some environmental impacts of their actions such as the protection of water resources (43*: -2), preventing nutrient losses (41: -1) or increasing organic matter (40: 0, consensus with viewpoint FO3a), impacts on soil organisms (34: -2), and environmental impacts in general (32: 0, consensus with viewpoint FO2). In stark contrast to others, viewpoint FO3b does not consider it important to enjoy their work (36*: -2). More in line with the other factors, viewpoint FO3b does not consider it important whether land is owned or not (11: -4, consensus with viewpoint FO1) or how far it is away from the farmstead (8: -3; consensus with viewpoints FO1 and FO2). Last, viewpoint FO3b does not shy away from the bureaucratic burden associated with farming (subsidies) (22: -4).

To conclude, viewpoint FO3b focuses on navigating the farm business in a way that reduces economic risks through their soil management, which includes making good use of the available subsidies. In comparison, environmental aspects are of low importance, as if the desire to enjoy the farm work.

Appendix D. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2026.109041>.

Data availability

The data are published in a repository, references are provided in the text.

References

- Adhikari, K., Hartemink, A.E., 2016. Linking soils to ecosystem services — a global review. *Geoderma* 262, 101–111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoderma.2015.08.009>.
- Amundson, R., Berhe, A.A., Hoppmans, J.W., Olson, C., Sztein, A.E., Sparks, D.L., 2015. Soil and human security in the 21st century. *Science* (80) 348, 1261071. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1261071>.
- Banasick, S., 2019. KADE: a desktop application for q methodology. *J. Open Source Softw.* 4, 1360. <https://doi.org/10.21105/JOSS.01360>.
- Barnes, A.P., Thompson, B., Toma, L., 2022. Finding the ecological farmer: a farmer typology to understand ecological practice adoption within Europe. *Curr. Res. Environ. Sustain.* 4, 100125. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crsust.2022.100125>.
- Bartkowski, B., Bartke, S., 2018. Leverage points for governing agricultural soils: a review of empirical studies of European farmers decision-making. *Sustainability* 10, 3179. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10093179>.
- Bartkowski, B., Schüßler, C., Müller, B., 2022. Typologies of European farmers: approaches, methods and research gaps. *Reg. Environ. Chang.* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10113-022-01899-y>.
- Blackstock, K.L., Ingram, J., Burton, R., Brown, K.M., Slee, B., 2010. Understanding and influencing behaviour change by farmers to improve water quality. *Sci. Total Environ.* 408, 5631–5638. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2009.04.029>.
- Blanchet, G., Gavazov, K., Bragazza, L., Sinaj, S., 2016. Responses of soil properties and crop yields to different inorganic and organic amendments in a Swiss conventional farming system. *Agric. Ecosyst. Environ.* 230, 116–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2016.05.032>.
- Blanchy, G., Bragato, G., Di Bene, C., Jarvis, N., Larsbo, M., Meurer, K., Garré, S., 2023. Soil and crop management practices and the water regulation functions of soils: a qualitative synthesis of meta-analyses relevant to European agriculture. *Soil* 9, 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.5194/soil-9-1-2023>.
- Braitto, M., Leonhardt, H., Penker, M., Schauppenlehner-Kloyber, E., Thaler, G., Flint, C. G., 2020. The plurality of farmers' views on soil management calls for a policy mix. *Land Use Policy* 99, 104876. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104876>.
- Brodth, S., Klonsky, K., Tourte, L., 2006. Farmer goals and management styles: implications for advancing biologically based agriculture. *Agric. Syst.* 89, 90–105. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2005.08.005>.
- Brunson, J.C., Read, Q.D., 2020. ggalluvial: Alluvial plots in “ggplot2”.
- Bütikofer, N., 2023. Swiss farmers' views on the role of soil management to mitigate impacts of droughts and extreme precipitation. Master Thesis, Universität Bern.
- Bütikofer, N., Hacek, M., Heller, O., Leonhardt, H., Holzkämper, A., 2024. Ansichten von Schweizer Landwirtinnen und Landwirten zum Thema Bodenbearbeitung. *Agrar. Schweiz* 15, 279–287. <https://doi.org/10.34776/afs15-279>.
- Calvignac, C., Potier, V., Labarthe, P., 2025. Growing on digital soil: French farmers' everyday acquisition of new skills online. *Agric. Hum. Values* 42, 2111–2127. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-025-10758-5/TABLES/1>.
- Casagrande, M., Peigné, J., Payet, V., Mäder, P., Sans, F.X., Blanco-Moreno, J.M., Antichi, D., Barberi, P., Beeckman, A., Bigongiari, F., Cooper, J., Dierauer, H., Gascoyne, K., Grosse, M., Heß, J., Kranzler, A., Luik, A., Peetsmann, E., Surböck, A., Willekens, K., David, C., 2016. Organic farmers motivations and challenges for adopting conservation agriculture in Europe. *Org. Agric.* 6, 281–295. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13165-015-0136-0/TABLES/1>.
- Cullen, P., Ryan, M., O'Donoghue, C., Hynes, S., hUallacháin, D.Ó., Sheridan, H., 2020. Impact of farmer self-identity and attitudes on participation in agri-environment schemes. *Land Use Policy* 95, 104660. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104660>.
- Davies, B.B., Hodge, I.D., 2007. Exploring environmental perspectives in lowland agriculture: a Q methodology study in east Anglia, UK. *Ecol. Econ.* 61, 323–333. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2006.03.002>.
- Davies, B.B., Hodge, I.D., 2012. Shifting environmental perspectives in agriculture: repeated Q analysis and the stability of preference structures. *Ecol. Econ.* 83, 51–57. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2012.08.013>.
- de Cárcer, P.S., Sinaj, S., Santonja, M., Fossati, D., Jeangros, B., 2019. Long-term effects of crop succession, soil tillage and climate on wheat yield and soil properties. *Soil Tillage Res.* 190, 209–219. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.still.2019.01.012>.
- Dessart, F.J., Barreiro-Hurlé, J., Van Bavel, R., 2019. Behavioural factors affecting the adoption of sustainable farming practices: a policy-oriented review. *Eur. Rev. Agric. Econ.* 46, 417–471. <https://doi.org/10.1093/erae/jbz019>.
- Dieteren, C.M., Patty, N.J.S., Reckers-Droog, V.T., van Exel, J., 2023. Methodological choices in applications of Q methodology: a systematic literature review. *Soc. Sci. Humanit. Open* 7, 100404. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaoh.2023.100404>.
- Dominati, E., Patterson, M., Mackay, A., 2010. A framework for classifying and quantifying the natural capital and ecosystem services of soils. *Ecol. Econ.* 69, 1858–1868. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2010.05.002>.
- EC, 2026. EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe [WWW Document]. URL https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/eu-missions-horizon-europe/soil-deal-europe_en (accessed 7.26.24).
- Emtage, N., Herbohn, J., Harrison, S., 2007. Landholder profiling and typologies for natural resource-management policy and program support: potential and constraints. *Environ. Manag.* 40, 481–492. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-005-0359-z>.
- Fielke, S., Taylor, B., Jakku, E., 2020. Digitalisation of agricultural knowledge and advice networks: a state-of-the-art review. *Agric. Syst.* 180, 102763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2019.102763>.
- Foguesatto, C.R., Borges, J.A.R., Machado, J.A.D., 2020. A review and some reflections on farmers' adoption of sustainable agricultural practices worldwide. *Sci. Total Environ.* 729, 138831. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138831>.
- Gorton, M., Douarin, E., Davidova, S., Latruffe, L., 2008. Attitudes to agricultural policy and farming futures in the context of the 2003 CAP reform: a comparison of farmers in selected established and new member states. *J. Rural. Stud.* 24, 322–336. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2007.10.001>.
- Guilleme, E.E., Barnes, A.P., Rounsevell, M.D.A., Renwick, A., 2012. Refining perception-based farmer typologies with the analysis of past census data. *J. Environ. Manag.* 110, 226–235. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2012.06.020>.
- Happel, M., Orsi, F., Hartmann, T., Bakker, M., 2022. Fertile ground, complex matter: plurality of farmers' attitudes towards green waste application as sustainable soil management. *Sociol. Rural.* 62, 509–541. <https://doi.org/10.1111/soru.12381>.
- Heller, O., Di Bene, C., Nino, P., Huyghebaert, B., Arlauskienė, A., Castanha, N.L., Higgins, S., Horel, A., Kir, A., Kizeková, M., Lacoste, M., Munkholm, L.J., O'Sullivan, L., Radzikowski, P., Rodríguez-Cruz, M.S., Sandén, T., Šarūnaitė, L., Seidel, F., Spiegel, H., Stalenga, J., Uusi-Kämpä, J., Vervuurt, W., Keller, T., Vanwindekens, F., 2024. Towards enhanced adoption of soil-improving management practices in Europe. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 75, e13483. <https://doi.org/10.1111/EJSS.13483>.
- Heuser, D.I., 2022. Soil governance in current European union law and in the European green deal. *Soil Secur.* 6, 100053. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.soisec.2022.100053>.
- Huber, R., Bartkowski, B., Brown, C., El Benni, N., Feil, J.-H., Grohmann, P., Joemann, I., Leonhardt, H., Mitter, H., Müller, B., 2024. Farm typologies for understanding farm systems and improving agricultural policy. *Agric. Syst.* 213, 103800. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agsy.2023.103800>.
- Iversen, S.V., Dalgaard, T., Graversgaard, M., 2024. Discordance between farmers and scientists - perspectives on nitrogen reduction measures in Denmark. *J. Environ. Manag.* 352, 119877. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2023.119877>.
- Khurajam, S., Wechtler, H., Higgins, V., Seshadri, B., 2025. Understanding the impact of identity and socio-economic factors on the adoption of soil conservation practices: empirical evidence from Australia. *J. Rural. Stud.* 116, 103636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2025.103636>.
- Klebl, F., Feindt, P.H., Piorr, A., 2024. Farmers behavioural determinants of on-farm biodiversity management in Europe: a systematic review. *Agric. Hum. Values* 41, 831–861. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-023-10505-8>.
- Klerkx, L., Petter Stræte, E., Kvam, G.T., Ystad, E., Butli Hårstad, R.M., 2017. Achieving best-fit configurations through advisory subsystems in AKIS: case studies of advisory service provisioning for diverse types of farmers in Norway. *J. Agric. Educ. Ext.* 23, 213–229. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2017.1320640>.
- Knierim, A., Boening, K., Caggiano, M., Cristóvão, A., Dirimanova, V., Koehnen, T., Labarthe, P., Prager, K., 2015. The AKIS concept and its relevance in selected EU member states. *Outlook Agric.* 44, 29–36. <https://doi.org/10.5367/OA.2015.0194>.
- Lahti, L., Huovari, J., Kainu, M., Biecek, P., 2017. Retrieval and analysis of Eurostat open data with the Eurostat package. *R J* 9, 385. <https://doi.org/10.32614/RJ-2017-019>.
- Lahti, L., Huovari, J., Kainu, M., Biecek, P., Hernangomez, D., Antal, D., Kantanen, P., 2023. Eurostat: Tools for Eurostat Open Data.
- Leonhardt, H., Braitto, M., Uehleke, R., 2022. Combining the best of two methodological worlds? Integrating Q methodology-based farmer archetypes in a quantitative model of agri-environmental scheme uptake. *Agric. Hum. Values* 39, 217–232. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-021-10242-w>.
- Leonhardt, Heidi, Braitto, M., Hacek, M., Schreiber, M., 2025. Food production, economic efficiency, soil health: soil management priorities of farmers in the Weinviertel region. *Austrian J. Agric. Econ. Rural Stud.* 34 (7), 59–66. <https://doi.org/10.15203/OEGA.34.7>.
- Leonhardt, H., Braitto, M., Bütikofer, N., Graversgaard, M., Höckert, J., Lunar Koch, E.J., Lundström, C., Schreiber, M., Tiselius, M., 2025a. Q sortings of factors influencing farmers' soil management - SoilX WP4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15730034>.
- Leonhardt, H., Braitto, M., Bütikofer, N., Graversgaard, M., Hacek, M., Höckert, J., Lunar Koch, E.J., Lundström, C., Schreiber, M., Tiselius, M., 2025b. Farm structural information and questionnaire responses - SoilX WP4. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15730136>.
- Leonhardt, H., Braitto, M., Graversgaard, M., Höckert, J., Lundström, C., Schreiber, M., 2025c. SoilX WP4: Interview guideline and questionnaire instrument. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15682965>.
- Lu, J., Ranjan, P., Floress, K., Ar buckle, J.G., Church, S.P., Eanes, F.R., Gao, Y., Gramig, B.M., Singh, A.S., Prokopy, L.S., 2022. A meta-analysis of agricultural conservation intentions, behaviors, and practices: insights from 35 years of quantitative literature in the United States. *J. Environ. Manag.* 323, 116240. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116240>.
- Lunar-Koch, E., 2024. Exploring motivational factors for soil protection measures by farmers in the Spanish region of Guadálajara: A Q-methodology approach. Master Thesis, Universität für Bodenkultur Wien.
- Lyle, G., 2015. Understanding the nested, multi-scale, spatial and hierarchical nature of future climate change adaptation decision making in agricultural regions: a narrative literature review. *J. Rural. Stud.* 37, 38–49. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2014.10.004>.
- Mayberry, D., Crase, L., Gullifer, C., 2005. Categorising farming values as economic, conservation and lifestyle. *J. Econ. Psychol.* 26, 59–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joep.2003.10.001>.

- McKeown, B.F., Thomas, D.B., 2013. *Q Methodology*. SAGE Publications, Incorporated, Thousand Oaks, California.
- Metzger, M.J., Shkaruba, A.D., Jongman, R.H.G., Bunce, R.G.H., 2012. Descriptions of the European Environmental Zones and Strata. Wageningen.
- Mills, J., Gaskell, P., Ingram, J., Dwyer, J., Reed, M., Short, C., 2017. Engaging farmers in environmental management through a better understanding of behaviour. *Agric. Hum. Values* 34, 283–299. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10460-016-9705-4>.
- Mukherjee, N., Zabala, A., Hüge, J., Nyumba, T.O., Adem Esmail, B., Sutherland, W.J., 2018. Comparison of techniques for eliciting views and judgements in decision-making. *Methods Ecol. Evol.* 9, 54–63. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.12940>.
- Ober, C., Canessa, C., Frick, F., Sauer, J., 2025. The role of behavioural factors in accepting agri-environmental contracts – evidence from a Q-method and thematic analysis in Germany. *Ecol. Econ.* 231, 108544. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2025.108544>.
- Oberlack, C., Pedde, S., Piemontese, L., Václavík, T., Sietz, D., 2023. Archetypes in support of tailoring land-use policies. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 18, 060202. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/acd802>.
- Pedersen, A.B., Nielsen, H.Ø., Daugbjerg, C., 2020. Environmental policy mixes and target group heterogeneity: analysing Danish farmers responses to the pesticide taxes. *J. Environ. Policy Plan.* 22, 608–619. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2020.1806047>.
- Prokopy, L.S., Floress, K., Klothor-Weinkauff, D., Baumgart-Getz, A., 2008. Determinants of agricultural best management practice adoption: evidence from the literature. *J. Soil Water Conserv.* 63, 300–311. <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.63.5.300>.
- Prokopy, L.S., Floress, K., Arbuckle, J.G., Church, S.P., Eanes, F.R., Gao, Y., Gramig, B.M., Ranjan, P., Singh, A.S., 2019. Adoption of agricultural conservation practices in the United States: evidence from 35 years of quantitative literature. *J. Soil Water Conserv.* 74, 520–534. <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.74.5.520>.
- R Core Team, 2021. *R: A language and environment for statistical computing*.
- Ranjan, P., Church, S.P., Floress, K., Prokopy, L.S., 2019. Synthesizing conservation motivations and barriers: what have we learned from qualitative studies of farmers behaviors in the United States? *Soc. Nat. Resour.* 32, 1171–1199. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2019.1648710>.
- Reimer, A., Thompson, A., Prokopy, L.S., Arbuckle, J.G., Genskow, K., Jackson-Smith, D., Lynne, G., McCann, L., Morton, L.W., Nowak, P., 2014. People, place, behavior, and context: a research agenda for expanding our understanding of what motivates farmers' conservation behaviors. *J. Soil Water Conserv.* 69, 57A–61A. <https://doi.org/10.2489/jswc.69.2.57A>.
- Rust, N.A., Ptak, E.N., Graversgaard, M., Iversen, S., Reed, M.S., de Vries, J.R., Ingram, J., Mills, J., Neumann, R.K., Kjeldsen, C., Muro, M., Dalgaard, T., 2020. Social capital factors affecting uptake of sustainable soil management practices: a literature review. *Emerald Open Res.* 1. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EOR-10-2023-0002>.
- Rust, N.A., Stankovics, P., Jarvis, R.M., Morris-Trainor, Z., de Vries, J.R., Ingram, J., Mills, J., Glikman, J.A., Parkinson, J., Toth, Z., Hansda, R., McMorran, R., Glass, J., Reed, M.S., 2022. Have farmers had enough of experts? *Environ. Manag.* 69, 31–44. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S00267-021-01546-Y/FIGURES/1>.
- Schreiber, M., Hacek, M., Höckert, J., Lundström, C., Tiselius, M., Quiñones-Ruiz, X.F., Leonhardt, H., 2026. Who do you strive to be? Exploring norms of good farming for sustainable soil management in four European regions. *Eur. J. Soil Sci.* 77, e70318. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ejss.70318>.
- Seghezze, L., Sneegas, G., Jepson, W., Brannstrom, C., Beckner, S., Lee, K., 2023. The use and potential of Q method in environmental planning and management. *J. Environ. Plan. Manag.* 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09640568.2023.2207727>.
- Serebrennikov, D., Thorne, F., Kallas, Z., McCarthy, S.N., 2020. Factors influencing adoption of sustainable farming practices in Europe: a systemic review of empirical literature. *Sustainability* 12, 9719. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12229719>.
- Sneegas, G., Beckner, S., Brannstrom, C., Jepson, W., Lee, K., Seghezze, L., 2021. Using Q-methodology in environmental sustainability research: a bibliometric analysis and systematic review. *Ecol. Econ.* 180, 106864. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106864>.
- Soini, K., Diaz, C., Gandini, G., de Haas, Y., Lilja, T., Martin-Collado, D., Pizzi, F., Hiemstra, S.J., 2012. Developing a typology for local cattle breed farmers in Europe. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 129, 436–447. <https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1439-0388.2012.01009.X>.
- Stræte, E.P., Hansen, B.G., Kvam, G.T., 2025. What is a farm? Mental framing and reframing as tools in communication between agricultural advisors and farmers. *J. Agric. Educ. Ext.* 31, 371–391. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2024.2382742>.
- Sutherland, L.A., Labarthe, P., 2022. Introducing 'microAKIS': a farmer-centric approach to understanding the contribution of advice to agricultural innovation. *J. Agric. Educ. Ext.* 28, 525–547. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1389224X.2022.2121903>.
- Thompson, B., Barnes, A.P., Toma, L., 2022. Increasing the adoption intensity of sustainable agricultural practices in Europe: farm and practice level insights. *J. Environ. Manag.* 320, 115663. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115663>.
- Usher, E.M., Church, S.P., Getson, J.M., Prokopy, L., 2023. The use of Q methodology as a participatory tool in natural resources management. *Soc. Nat. Resour.* 36, 879–890. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08941920.2023.2191229>.
- Vecchio, Y., Di Pasquale, J., Del Giudice, T., Pauselli, G., Masi, M., Adinolfi, F., 2022. Precision farming: what do Italian farmers really think? An application of the Q methodology. *Agric. Syst.* 201, 103466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.AGSY.2022.103466>.
- Verheijen, F.G.A., Jones, R.J.A., Rickson, R.J., Smith, C.J., 2009. Tolerable versus actual soil erosion rates in Europe. *Earth-Science Rev.* 94, 23–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2009.02.003>.
- Walder, P., Kantelhardt, J., 2018. The environmental behaviour of farmers – capturing the diversity of perspectives with a Q methodological approach. *Ecol. Econ.* 143, 55–63. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.06.018>.
- Watts, S., Stenner, P., 2012. *Doing Q Methodological Research: Theory, Method & Interpretation*. SAGE Publications Ltd, London.
- Webler, T., Danielson, S., Tuler, S., 2009. Using Q Method to Reveal Social Perspectives in Environmental Research [WWW Document]. *Soc. Environ. Res. Inst.* URL <https://www.betterevaluation.org/sites/default/files/Qprimer.pdf> (accessed 10.20.25).
- Wickham, H., 2016. *ggplot2: Elegant Graphics for Data Analysis*. Springer-Verlag, New York.
- Witzling, L., Shaw, B.R., Comito, J., Wald, D.M., Ripley, E., Stevenson, N., 2023. Promoting agricultural conservation on Facebook: an exploration of the performance of farmer identity frames across age and gender. *Sustain. Sci.* 18, 2677–2689. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11625-023-01416-Y/TABLES/5>.
- Zabala, A., Sandbrook, C., Mukherjee, N., 2018. When and how to use Q methodology to understand perspectives in conservation research. *Conserv. Biol.* 32, 1185–1194. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.13123>.